

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869821

D8.1

First version of the communication and dissemination plan

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Date: 02/12/2020

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D8.1. First version of the communication and dissemination plan

Summary		
<p>Minimal Size Thermal and Electrical Energy Storage System for In-Situ Residential Installation MiniStor is a project funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme to offer a sustainable solution to harness the energy efficiency potential of the European building stock.</p> <p>MiniStor aims at designing and producing a novel compact integrated thermal storage system for achieving sustainable heating, cooling and electricity storage. Eighteen partners across the EU, Switzerland and the UK work together to harness the large potential of new and existing EU buildings providing an innovative solution for all.</p>		
Deliverable Number	Work Package	
D8.1	WP. 8	
Lead Beneficiary	Deliverable Author(S)	
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Planned Delivery Date	Actual Delivery Date	
30/10/2020	02/12/2020	
Classification This report is...	Draft	X
	Final	
	Confidential	
	Restricted	
	Public	X

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
1.0	21/10/2020	Draft Version	First integrated version	FEUGA
2.0	26/10/2020	Draft Version	Comments (Internal)	FEUGA
3.0	24/11/2020	Draft Version	Comments	IERC
4.0	30/10/2020	Draft Version	Incorporating comments and finalizing the deliverable	FEUGA
5.0	01/12/2020	Draft Version	Final comments	IERC
6.0	02/12/2020	Final version	Deliverable finalization	FEUGA

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Minimal Size Thermal and Electrical Energy Storage System for In-Situ Residential Installation is a 54 months long project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme to offer a sustainable solution to harness the energy efficiency potential of the European building stock. During the development of the project, the MiniStor system will be demonstrated and validated in five demonstration sites located in Ireland, Spain, Greece and Hungary to test its effectiveness at different local climatic conditions, facilitating market replication while offering an innovative, efficient and clean thermal and electrical energy storage solution for all Europeans.

The objective of this deliverable is to outline MiniStor's plan for communication and dissemination activities to be carried out during the development of the project and ensure its impact beyond the project's lifetime.

This communication and dissemination plan will create a strategy to reach out to the highlighted target audiences, achieve MiniStor's objectives with key messages, communication products and channels, at the right time while establishing the consortium responsibilities and ensure the correct compliance with the key performance indicators (KPIs) already agreed upon by the consortium. This document includes the *Communication Guidelines* and *Book of Style* addressing the MiniStor visual identity that were made available to the consortium in the first months of the project.

Together with the communication and dissemination plan, the document provides a summary of the MiniStor project as a whole as well as the overall project and work package objectives. MiniStor dissemination and communication plan is detailed, by first outlining the visual identity of the project, then highlighting the role of the consortium partners and its involvement alongside the development of the project. The communication and dissemination plan will be divided into five phases, each of them focused on specific aspects centered on the availability of results and stakeholders network capacity building: the initial awareness phase (M1-M14), the strategic dissemination phase (M14-M26), the mid-project results oriented dissemination (M26-M30), the second strategic dissemination phase (M30-M42), and finally the final results exploitation phase (M42-M54). As said, the final goal of these phases is to structure the efforts based on the availability of results, therefore, these phases will fluctuate alongside the development of the rest of the work packages. This deliverable covers partially a good part of the first phase, setting the tools and procedures that will enable both internal and external communication and dissemination for the duration of the project that have been already defined, analyzed and agreed upon by the MiniStor consortium partners.

This plan will serve as a 'living document' throughout the project, offering guidance and a base regarding the communication and dissemination efforts carried out by the consortium.

This deliverable (D8.1) includes the communication and dissemination plan created by FEUGA with the contribution of all consortium partners since the onset of the project. A formal update of the deliverable will be provided mid-project to be aligned with the first draft of the PEDR. At the end of the project, a final version will be presented (D8.2) in coordination with the final PEDR, together with the products and results of each communication and dissemination activity, reporting as well future-oriented dissemination and communication activities, foreseen by each project partner and the work package leader, to ensure the continuation of the project's impact beyond its lifetime.

1. INTRODUCTION

This document is the deliverable *D8.1 First version of the communication and dissemination plan* of the MiniStor project. It lays out the dissemination and communication tools, channels, messages, timings and objectives to provide a strong base and guideline for all consortium partners to achieve the highest level of impact possible for the project, during its duration and beyond.

The dissemination and communication strategy has five phases:

- an initial awareness phase (M1-M14),
- a strategic dissemination phase (M14-M26),
- a mid-project results-oriented dissemination (M26-M30),
- a second strategic dissemination phase (M30-M42) and finally
- a results dissemination phase (M42-M54).

This plan will ensure that the members of the consortium will take a proactive role in the overall efforts to maximize, to extend possible, the outreach of the project. This is being achieved through participating, with the right messages and channels, in relevant workshops, conferences and other events, as well as publishing project results and general articles in relevant specific and general media. All actions aim at achieving a well-designed European coverage either at a local, national or European level where all stakeholders are addressed accordingly to their needs and most appropriate tools. This deliverable also covers the means used to track all activities to ensure compliance with the KPIs and with the open access requirements.

Consortium members are also required to organize events where project progress and results are presented ensuring the possibility of networking with stakeholder groups of relevance at local, national and European level, as describe in this document. Tools and products for online and physical dissemination and communication activities are to be made available, and adapted as needed, to adjust to the specific needs of each stakeholder group's local/national conditions.

1.1. Purpose and objectives

The European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme is aware that communication plays an important role in ensuring European projects have real and lasting impact. Communication is important not only to ensure transparency and the exchange of knowledge but also to contribute to a stronger visibility of the EU Research and Innovation activities and efforts to bring science and technological development closer to the public and to cause a positive change in the lives of all Europeans. Indeed, all dissemination and communication activities carried out by MiniStor must be a product of a shared effort developed by all members of the consortium.

Dissemination and communication activities are a core part of any H2020 project. Therefore, to have specific, clear and measurable objectives and well identified target audiences and messages are fundamental for the success of any communication and dissemination strategy. All the activities presented in this document are aligned with the major project milestones to maximize the impact of the project. By carrying out dissemination and communication activities simultaneously with ongoing research activities, a constant relationship is maintained with the work effectuated by the rest of the work packages. The communication and dissemination activities are subjected to the availability of results and

relevance to stakeholders with a special attention being given to policy-makers, researchers and other H2020 projects.

This Communication and Dissemination plan is delivered in M13 of the project and it provides a framework for all partners, although the book of style and a preliminary Communication Strategy were shared and agreed upon by all partners during the first months of the project (M6), to help to effectively communicate and report all relevant activities and outcomes and offer guidance on the overall how-to-do of the project materials. Even though this plan is rooted in the Description of Action, it will be refined and updated through the project duration in order to reflect the project's progress, possible new opportunities and change of circumstances and needs.

The main objectives of this communication and dissemination plan are:

- Organize and guarantee an effective communication of the project messages, results and activities at a local, national and EU level.
- Identify appropriate target groups to address the communication and dissemination messages together with the tools, products, timing and channels to do so effectively.
- Implement a recognizable visual identity of the MiniStor project together with guidelines to do so correctly.
- Present the communication and dissemination KPIs previously agreed by the MiniStor consortium, useful and needed to measure the effectiveness of those quantifiable activities.
- Illustrate how the project will cooperate and interact in the residential energy efficiency sector ensuring a broad impact of the project and the prevalence of its results beyond project time.
- Update the communication and dissemination plan as needed to adapt to the circumstances that may arise during the development of the project.

Apart from the communication and dissemination plan, this deliverable includes key communication and dissemination materials, templates and report mechanisms that have been already made available to consortium partners, in order to provide a consistent visual identity and a strong strategic approach when it comes to executing communication and dissemination activities, as well as reporting them correctly.

1.2. Structure of the document

This document is divided into five main sections. The first section 'Introduction' covers the purpose, objectives, and relevant details for the understanding of the document (acronyms and partner's abbreviations). The following section 'background' gives a general overview of the project summary and the objectives of the work package from which the communication and dissemination plan belongs. The third section of this deliverable presents the basics of the visual identity of the project that play a fundamental role in the design of the central section of this document: 'the communication and dissemination plan' itself.

The communication and dissemination plan section covers the fundamental objectives, target audience, key messages and channels of the plan to the specific materials and configuration of the online and physical presence of the project. This section also deals with the key performance indicators, reported activities and the monitoring and reporting tools set for this project.

The final section 'conclusion' offers a summary of the information presented in the overall document.

1.3. Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader
DoA	Description of action (Grant Agreement Annex 1 Part A)
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
M	Month
D	Deliverable
H2020	Horizon 2020 programme
PEDR	Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of the project Results
TMC	Thermochemical material
PCM	Phase-change materials
RES	Renewable energy sources
PVT	Photovoltaic thermal panels
HEMS	Home energy management system
PPT	Power Point
ICT	Information and communications technology

1.4. Partners list and abbreviations

Abbreviation	Partner
IERC	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK - NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, CORK
CERTH	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS
CNRS-PROMES	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS
HSLU	FACHHOCHSCHULE ZENTRALSCHWEIZ - HOCHSCHULE LUZERN
CARTIF	FUNDACION CARTIF
SUNLTD	SUNAMP LIMITED
SUNCH	SUNAMP SWITZERLAND GMBH
EDILIANS	EDILIANS
ENDEF	ENDEF ENGINEERING SL
ENETECH	ENETECH SPOLKA Z OGRANICZONA ODPOWIEDZIALNOSCIA
SGS TECNOS	SGS TECNOS SA
EMI	EMI EPITESUGYI MINOSEGELLENORZO INNOVACIOS NONPROFIT KFT
WOODSPRING	FAFORRAS FAIPARI KORLATOLT FELELOSSÉGU TARSASAG
CORKCITY	CORK CITY COUNCIL
DUTH	DIMOKRITIO PANEPISTIMIO THRAKIS
FEUGA	FUNDACION EMPRESA UNIVERSIDAD GALLEGA
R2M	R2M SOLUTION SRL
UEDIN	THE UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH

2. BACKGROUND

2.1. Project summary

Minimal Size Thermal and Electrical Energy Storage System for In-Situ Residential Installation (MiniStor) is a 54-month project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme to offer a sustainable solution to harness the energy efficiency potential of the European building stock.

The overall objective of the MiniStor project is to design and develop a novel compact, integrated thermal storage system for achieving sustainable heating, cooling and electricity storage that can be adapted to new and existing residential buildings. The thermal storage system will be based on a high-performing CaCl₂/NH₃ thermochemical material (TCM) reaction, combined with hot and latent heat storage based on phase-change materials (PCM). The electrical storage will be a conventional system based on a Li-ion battery for flexibility and usage year-round. The storage system allows for compact storing of RES-based energy such as hybrid photovoltaic thermal panels (PVT). Furthermore, the proposed system includes a home energy management system (HEMS) to synchronize and efficiently manage the overall supply and demand at household level, responding for grid constraints and price signals. The system will provide stability, performance and use of at least 20 years.

2.2. WP8 objectives

MiniStor Work Package 8 (WP8) will not only communicate and disseminate project results to the general public and specialized audiences, it also aims to foster collaboration with similar projects, helping to understand common hurdles. This WP will identify cooperation and contribution models as well as other cross cutting priorities such as Clean Energy and Open Innovation.

Work Package 8 covers the communication and dissemination activities of the MiniStor project related to its existence and results to the relevant stakeholders and civil society. The main objectives of this WP are, as defined in the DoA:

- To define and implement the communication and dissemination strategy.
- To promote project acceptance through standardization and relevant policy-influencing bodies highlighting innovation potential of the system.
- To link MiniStor with existing networks, projects and initiatives to promote an effective and efficient transfer of knowledge and to find common solutions to challenges posed by current regulations that are based on conventional technologies.

This document focuses on objective 1 'To define and implement the communication and dissemination strategy'. The dissemination and communication strategy will be devised with one main objective in mind: achieving the maximum possible outreach within the allocated budget and resources, among the target group of stakeholders identified in this document. It should be in line with the 4 processes: define a clear set of objectives and messages to be disseminated; identify and address the target stakeholder groups; identify and correctly use the best channels and tools at the correct timing; evaluate, report, analyze and adapt to the conditions at each given time.

3. MiniStor VISUAL IDENTITY

The visual identity of a European project is fundamental as it is the recognizable face of the project and its work. More than a name, a design or a symbol, a brand is the recognizable face of the project. Branding helps to identify a project and distinguish it from other initiatives. The most important reason for developing branding is to generate project recognition. A name, visual identity, a recognized brand can elevate the perceived quality of a Project.

Visual identity is one of the most important aspects of the brand. The care, normalization and homogenization of the visual identity of our project will allow us among other aspects:

- Promote stakeholder recognition
- Enhance credibility in the project’s actions and results
- Ensure quality and reliability of the project
- Inspire a sense of belonging to a group with shared interests

The following indications are a tool to achieve excellence in the use of the MiniStor brand maintaining consistency and avoiding deviations in the different uses.

3.1. MiniStor Logo and EU Emblem

MiniStor’s logo together with the EU emblem must be used in all communication and dissemination products involving the project. It was made available to all consortium partners, in M3, the book of style with the guidelines, products and templates needed to build the MiniStor visual identity. This document, the book of style, offers indications are a tool to achieve excellence in the use of MiniStor’s brand avoiding deviations in the different uses.

Figure 1. MiniStor main logo (Full Logotype)

As said, if the format of the communication material background does not allow the use of the Full Logotype, partners are welcome to use a one-ink version of the logotype:

Figure 2. MiniStor logo One-ink versions

Considering the conditions of the Grant Agreement, there is an obligation to acknowledge the EU with certain specific wording and emblems. This is a commitment to carry out communication actions to maximize their impact, and ensure the transparency and visibility of their funding, activities and results. Therefore, any communication action or material created by the project must clearly indicate the source of the funds. For this reason, all European projects must use the European emblem (flag), alongside text to indicate the name of the programme from which the project has received funding for MiniStor, this text reads as follows: **This project has received funding from the European Union’s H2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 869821**

The EU Emblem will be located, preferably, on the left of the full logotype always ensuring both the MiniStor logo and EU Emblem are equal in terms of size and visibility, whenever possible.

Figure 3. Suggested use of MiniStor logo in co-existence with EU emblem

3.2. Typography and corporate colours

Together with the MiniStor logo and the EU emblem use and acknowledgment, the corporate colors and the typography play a fundamental role in the MiniStor overall visual identity. The palette of primary colors below has been developed comprising a “One Voice” color scheme. A consistent use of these colors will contribute to the cohesive and harmonious look of MiniStor identity. The corporate colors of MiniStor trademark are as follows, a gradient blue and red as primary colors:

BLUE COLOUR CODES

CMYK: C081 M002 Y011 K000
 Pantone: 638 C
 RGB: R000 G173 B216
 Web: #00acd7

RED COLOUR CODES

CMYK: C000 M083 Y073 K000
 Pantone: Warm Red C
 RGB: R233 G071 B063
 Web: #e8473e

The Secondary colors are complementary to the official colors, but are not recognizable identifiers for MiniStor. The MiniStor secondary colors are black, white and grey.

Regarding the typography, this plays an important role in communicating an overall tone and quality. A careful use of typography reinforces and ensures clarity and harmony in all MiniStor communications.

We have selected a personalized font for the logo. The font *Lato* was selected for other corporate applications, if not possible, Calibri will be used.

Figure 4. Corporate font of the project (Lato)

A personalized font was specially created for the logo:

CORPORATE FONT 01
Personalized Font

Figure 5. Personalized font for MiniStor logotype

3.3. MiniStor Templates

Together with the book of style (M3) these also made available to the consortium partners in the common shared platform Microsoft Teams, along with, basic templates with the visual identity of the project. These are shown in the following figures. Alternate, but brand-appropriate templates can be considered during the deployment of the project to accommodate the needs of the partners and requirements of the stakeholders at a local, national and European level, where required.

DELIVERABLE TEMPLATE

Figure 6. Designed MiniStor deliverable template

AGENDA TEMPLATE

Agenda | Title of the meeting

Meeting description	
Meeting number	Example
Meeting title	Brief description and objectives of the meeting
Date	Example
Time	00:00h
Location	Example
Chair	Drift/Real
Responsible	Example/Label
Attendees	
Chair/organiser	Name, Surname, Affiliation
Attendees	Name, Surname, Affiliation Name, Surname, Affiliation
	Name, Surname, Affiliation
Detailed agenda	
Item 1	Example
Item 2	Example
Item 3	Example

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101015111

Figure 7. Designed MiniStor Agenda template

PPT TEMPLATE

MiniStor

PRESENTATION

DESCRIPTION HERE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101015111

82%

FEATURE CONTENT

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Aliquam tincidunt ante nec sem congue conwallis. Pellentesque vel mauris quis nisl ornare rutrum in id risus. Proin vehicula ut sem et tempus. Interdum et malesuada fames ac ante ipsum primis in faucibus. Pellentesque.

- ✔ Lorem ipsum has two main data statistical this methodologies important. Data analysis which summarizes.
- ✔ Lorem ipsum has two main data statistical this methodologies important. Data analysis which summarizes.
- ✔ Lorem ipsum has two main data statistical this methodologies important. Data analysis which summarizes.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101015111

The slide features a large, stylized leaf graphic on the left side. On the right, there is a section titled "miniStor PRESENT" with a subtitle "Your great subtitle in this line". Below this, there are four data points represented by percentages: 72%, 64%, 78%, and 91%. Each percentage is accompanied by a vertical bar and a short paragraph of Lorem Ipsum text. At the bottom of the slide, there is a section titled "FEATURE CONTENT" with a paragraph of Lorem Ipsum text. Below the text is a photograph of several white house models on a table. In the bottom right corner, there is a small logo and a text box indicating funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

Figure 8. Designed MiniStor PPT Template

LIST OF ATTENDEES TEMPLATE

The template includes the miniStor logo and a funding notice in the top left. The main content is a table titled "List of attendees" with a subtitle "TITLE OF THE MEETING/ WORKSHOP". The table has five columns: NUMBER, SURNAME, NAME, ORGANIZATION, and SIGNATURE. The table is currently empty, with 10 rows for data entry. A page number "1" is located at the bottom center.

NUMBER	SURNAME	NAME	ORGANIZATION	SIGNATURE

Figure 9. Designed MiniStor list of attendee's template

LETTER TEMPLATE

The letter template features the miniStor logo at the top center. The background is a light gray with a faint, large watermark of the miniStor logo. At the bottom, there is a small footer area with a logo and some text.

Figure 10. Designed MiniStor Letter template

4. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PLAN

Dissemination and communication is designed as a forerunner activity to ensure knowledge dissemination and stakeholder engagement. Indeed, to foster the impact of the project on targeted end-users, the project must be broadly communicated and disseminated. The present plan will involve all activities by which project-related results and general knowledge is provided to relevant stakeholders and general public at a local, national and European level.

In this document, and as indicated by the guidelines of H2020 projects¹, the communication activities have as a main objective the promotion of the project results and general information on its development addressing the general public and mass media via a non-specialized language and channels of general use (social media, website, newsletters and magazines, among others). The dissemination activities also refer to the public disclosure of results to a specific and specialized target audience (scientific communities, industry stakeholders...) using scientific language and via specific channels (Peer-review journals, scientific conferences, MiniStor's website knowledge center, among others).

The outcome and success of these activities strongly relies on the channels identified in this document and the tools used to address the targeted stakeholders. MiniStor will use a balance mix of traditional (printed dissemination materials, participation to events, scientific publications) and specialized, due to the current pandemic and travel restrictions, a strong online presence (via social media website, material published on other websites and online events). All material will be adjusted to each stakeholder group and will be regularly analyzed and adapted as each project partner shall see fit.

This document will be regularly updated to accommodate the strategies for each type of partner once the results of the project become available.

4.1. MiniStor Communication and Dissemination plan

The communication actions developed under the project will be aligned with the MiniStor objectives and the general aims of the H2020 programme, which is to increase Europe's competitiveness through the implementation of three priorities²:

- Generate an excellent science
- Creating industrial leadership
- Addressing social challenges

¹ *Communicating Your Project - H2020 Online Manual* https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm

² *European Commission. Horizon 2020 structure and budget* https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/applying-for-funding/find-a-call/h2020-structure-and-budget_en.htm

The general objective should also be achieved through the specific objectives of "Spreading excellence and broadening participation", and "Science with and for society"³.

4.1.1. Objectives

MiniStor addresses the topic LC-EEB-05-2019-20: "Integrated storage systems for residential buildings" through the following target outcomes and how they are addressed: "Optimized storage solutions for thermal and electric energy are needed in order to better synchronize the overall supply and demand, at residential, district and urban level. Efficient management of the peak loads would reduce the overall operational costs of the installations."

Within this framework, MiniStor results will be disseminated for the purpose of reinforce the overall activities to be developed by the project:

- The design and application of an integrated, high performing, versatile, durable and multifunctional thermal energy storage system that reduces net energy consumption for heating and cooling.
- The development of a high energy density and compact TCM reactor for heating and cooling storage.
- The Integration of self-harvesting RES options, electrical energy flexibility and response to grid signals, offering increase of self-consumption and better synchronization of energy flows at a building level.
- The improvement of building performance through a cutting-edge human-centric home energy management system.
- The use of design and construction methods for decreased installation time with minimum maintenance needs.
- The development of an effective storage solution with minimum environmental impact.
- The deployment, demonstration, validation and evaluation of the overall solution in real-life residential sites.
- The elaboration and validation circular economy-driven business models (BMs) and market design to stimulate market penetration of the developed and validated integrated storage system at European level.

The communication and dissemination plan is structured to address a full range of potential actors playing different, but fundamental roles in residential energy efficiency, and innovation, energy storage solutions research including a human-centric perspective, policy maker authorities among others. These groups will be discussed in further detail in the coming section.

The MiniStor communication and dissemination plan should reflect and serve the general objectives of the project and its specific work package and will be adapted as required during the development of the project. The following objectives will be pursued by this plan:

COMMUNICATION OBJECTIVES

- Overall: Create public awareness and enhance the visibility of MiniStor

DISSEMINATION OBJECTIVES

- Overall: Facilitates industrial reuse of the results

³ European Commission. *Spreading Excellence and Widening Participation*
<https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/spreading-excellence-and-widening-participation>

project results, consortium and the research programme.

- To share project results as widely as possible.
 - To create awareness of the MiniStor project within its target groups and general public about its objectives, the consortium, countries involved, the main project activities.
 - To promote MiniStor brand, in order to enable the project's identification by an established image.
 - To identify and outline target groups, most appropriate channels for communication, timing, key messages and promotional materials.
 - To facilitate the integration and encourage the commitment among project partners in order to improve the quality and consistency of the share work
 - Encourage stakeholders to use project results, increasing the impact outreach.
 - To influence specific policies around project key aspects to facilitate the adoption and market outreach of the MiniStor system.
 - Create immediate, short/medium term commercial impact
- To reach as many target audiences as possible by promoting widely planned activities in order to maximize the number of stakeholders reached.
 - To seek relevant opportunities of collaboration with topic-related EU projects and initiatives to increase the general outreach of the project among stakeholders and to enrich its final outcomes.
 - To raise attention among key stakeholders on how MiniStor will design and develop a novel compact, integrated thermal storage system for achieving sustainable heating, cooling and electricity storage that can be adapted to new and existing residential buildings offering a sustainable and integrated solution to help the decarbonization of the heating and cooling sector, essential to reach and fulfil the EU's climate and energy goals, while fighting climate change and securing energy supply and provision.
 - Create long term scientific and commercial impact

4.1.2. Communication and dissemination approach: phases

The MiniStor communication and dissemination plan is structured in five main phases that can be adapted, as they are subjected to the availability of results and stakeholder engagement opportunities that may vary during the project development:

Time (Phase)	Objective	Approach
Awareness Stage 1 – Initial awareness phase Phase (M1 – M14)	Aims at: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating the visual identity of the project, promotional materials, website and social media networks; • Agreeing upon the communication Strategy, future activities and KPIs; • Creating initial awareness related with the Project’s objectives and scope; • Creating a first contact with Stakeholders via events and by building a network on social media. 	Creation of the visual identity of MiniStor and the promotional materials linked to it (ppt, agenda, list of attendees...) and linked to the main scope of the project and its consortium (website, project video, newsletters). Begin to build a network around the project to engage stakeholders (participation at events, social media networks, general articles, boost the website...)
Understanding and interest Stage 2 – Strategic dissemination Phase (M14 – M26)	Aims at: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create more “targeted awareness” regarding the MiniStor system to key stakeholders and potential users; • Inform policymakers and other EU projects and initiatives about the benefits of MiniStor; • Engage in strong collaborations with other EU projects and initiatives; • Continue to build a community around MiniStor social media and website to increase MiniStor activities outreach; • Continue to develop promotional activities to feed the increase in activities (e.g. events participations). 	Once set the basis and the channels, this phase focus on creating a more targeted awareness while keeping the efforts to increase the community, stakeholders engaged around MiniStor. This phase implies an increase in communication and dissemination actions in events and efforts to keep feeding social medial, the website and its outcomes, creating more promotional materials oriented to specific target groups.
Mid-project Results Stage 3 – Mid-project results oriented dissemination Phase (M26 – M30)	Aims at: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disseminate the preliminary project results available mid-project; • Create a momentum around the mid-project workshops to engage key stakeholders among them policymakers, scientific community and the residential sector. • Increase dissemination efforts by creating new products and participating actively in events, publications and networking efforts. 	The approach of this phase will focus on the mid-project workshops that will take place during M27. These events will ensure a broad engagement with targeted stakeholders and ensure the involvement of policymakers. Dissemination materials will be created and adapted to include the preliminary project results available
Strengthening Stage 4 – Second strategic dissemination phase	Aims at: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthening of the community of stakeholders created until the moment. • Maximize to the extent possible the stakeholder capacity outreach. 	Maintain the momentum created by the last phase to increase the stakeholder outreach and increase the MiniStor community. There is a special effort to be made in order to have the maximum outreach capacity to ensure the exploitation phase is a success.

<p>Phase (M30– M42)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase dissemination efforts by creating new products and participating actively in events, publications and networking efforts. • Active collaboration and relationship building with other EU projects and initiative. 	<p>A priority is given in activities related to networking, capacity building, events participation and the active presence on social media and website feeding.</p>
<p>Exploitation Stage 4 – Final results Phase (M42 – M54)</p>	<p>Aims at:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maximizing target stakeholder awareness regarding the MiniStor System and the project results. • Final update of dissemination products to accommodate final results. • Ensure involvement of key stakeholders to reach dissemination objectives and ensure the use of project results. 	<p>Final update of the dissemination products to accommodate the final results of the project. The approach will focus on targeted stakeholders in a more individualized and targeted manner to reach the dissemination objectives and ensure the project results are used and will be used beyond the project’s lifetime. The final project conference will take place and a stronger involvement of policymakers and market actors will be pursued.</p>

Table 1. MiniStor communication and dissemination plan phases description

This deliverable partially covers a significant part of the first phase, setting the tools and procedures that will enable both internal and external communication and dissemination for the duration of the project that have been already defined, analyzed and agreed upon by the MiniStor consortium partners.

4.1.3. Target audiences

The main objective of this communication and dissemination plan is to inform, reach out to society and show the benefits of the research being carried out within the project. This approach should be communicated to the general public and to the media in particular, as the latter may actively contribute to communication activities by informing society about the impact of the project's results.

Apart from the general public, a key group of interest for the dissemination activities are the stakeholders, due to their capacity to support and promote the activities of the project, ensure the use of the results during the project development and beyond, as well as their influence on the project and/or the wider target audiences.

In relation to the stakeholders, the following groups have been identified as the priority stakeholder groups of interest:

- Public authorities, public administrations, regulators, energy and regional development agencies.
- Associations and networks of stakeholder’s representatives.
- Building owners, direct end users, and other type of user profiles.
- RES integration developers, Consultancy companies, installers, renovators, inspectors and energy auditors, among others.
- Energy services companies and thermal/electric energy companies.
- Investors and financing institutions.
- ICT companies and service providers (large, small, start-ups).

- Wider research community – this will be addressed through scientific publications and participation in specialized conferences. An open access model will be preferred for scientific publications.

Due to the heterogeneous nature of the targeted audience, communication and dissemination actions will be adapted, identifying the most appropriate channels, tools and messages for each of the segmented audiences to reach the total of the addressees by means of public-message-medium alignment.

4.1.4. Key messages for each specific target group

These key messages will be updated during the development of the project to reflect its evolution and results. All key messages will address target stakeholders through all means possible, as displayed in this document:

Specific Key Messages	Targeted Stakeholder
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Integrated, high performing, versatile, durable and multifunctional thermal energy storage system. ▪ Cost-efficient energy storage systems. ▪ Circular economy-driven business models (BMs). ▪ Minimum environmental impact. ▪ Decreased installation time with minimum maintenance needs. ▪ Reduction of net energy consumption for heating and cooling. ▪ High energy density and compact TCM reactor for heating and cooling storage. ▪ Integration of self-harvesting RES options and electrical energy flexibility. ▪ Integration of response to grid signals. ▪ Increase of self-consumption. ▪ Better synchronization of energy flows at a building level. ▪ Improvement of building performance. ▪ Cutting-edge human-centric home energy management system. 	<p>Energy services companies and thermal/electric energy companies.</p> <p>ICT companies and service providers (large, small, start-ups).</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Support EU policies for boosting energy efficiency. ▪ Support EU policies for renovation of the EU building stock. ▪ Job creation. ▪ Circular economy-driven business models (BMs). ▪ Minimum environmental impact. ▪ Health benefits and wellbeing. ▪ Reduction of energy poverty. ▪ Reduction of net energy consumption for heating and cooling. ▪ Integrated, high performing, versatile, durable and multifunctional thermal energy storage system. ▪ Integration of self-harvesting RES options and electrical energy flexibility. ▪ Integration of response to grid signals. ▪ Increase of self-consumption. ▪ Improvement of building performance. 	<p>Public authorities, public administrations, regulators, Energy/regional development agencies.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Cutting-edge human-centric home energy management system. ▪ Increase of self-consumption. ▪ Health benefits and wellbeing. ▪ Reduction of energy poverty. ▪ Increased property value. ▪ Cost-efficient energy storage systems. 	<p>Associations and networks of stakeholder’s representatives.</p> <p>Building owners, direct end users, and other type of user profiles.</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduction of net energy consumption for heating and cooling. Integrated, high performing, versatile, durable and multifunctional thermal energy storage system. Minimum environmental impact. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integrated, high performing, versatile, durable and multifunctional thermal energy storage system. Decreased installation time with minimum maintenance needs. Cost-efficient energy storage systems. Reduction of net energy consumption for heating and cooling. High energy density and compact TCM reactor for heating and cooling storage. Integration of self-harvesting RES options and electrical energy flexibility. Integration of response to grid signals. Increase of self-consumption. Better synchronization of energy flows at a building level. Improvement of building performance. 	<p>RES integration developers, Consultancy companies, installers, renovators, inspectors and energy auditors, among others.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular economy-driven business models (BMs). Decreased installation time with minimum maintenance needs. Increased property value. Cost-efficient energy storage systems. Reduction of net energy consumption for heating and cooling. Integrated, high performing, versatile, durable and multifunctional thermal energy storage system. Integration of self-harvesting RES options and electrical energy flexibility. Integration of response to grid signals. Increase of self-consumption. Better synchronization of energy flows at a building level. Improvement of building performance. 	<p>Investors and financing institutions.</p>

Table 2. Relation between specific key messages and targeted stakeholders

4.1.5. Other Key messages (Impacts)

MiniStor expected impacts are to be used in all communication materials, when possible, through online channels and printed ones. The following research impacts might change according to how research advances. The communication messages linked to these messages will vary accordingly.

- ✓ Impact #1: Demonstrate solutions that have a stable, reliable long-term performance in multi-cyclic seasonal and use of at least 20 years.
Result: individual components have endured long-term multi-cyclic operation in their original operational environment.
- ✓ Impact #2: Deliver compact systems with the potential to fit in the limited space available in a single building in the existing housing stock or new buildings. The storage material volume per dwelling should not exceed 1 m³.
Result: Calculated volume of 0.72m³ of storage material.
- ✓ Impact #3: Solutions should demonstrate a potential to reduce the net energy consumption of a building by at least 25% and a have return-on-investment period below 10 years.
Result: Energy savings by at least 44% PE and return of investment of 6.7 years.
- ✓ Impact #4: Use of high energy density storage materials allowing storage densities up to 10 times higher than water (based on overall system efficiency).
Result: Energy storage density more than 13.5 times higher than water.

4.2. Communication and dissemination channels and materials

The use of appropriate channels for communication and dissemination as well as the tools and products are as important as the identification of the target audience and the key messages as described above. MiniStor will implement a multi-channel communication and dissemination approach.

The criteria to be taken into consideration when classifying and selecting the most appropriate communication channels are:

- The means used for each of the target groups.
- The means accessible to each target group.
- The most influential, and credible media among target groups.

Bearing these criteria in mind, and framing them within the project's needs, this section will offer an extensive rationale of the communication and dissemination planning in terms of specific channels, promotional materials available and the advancement achieved over the course of the past 12 months.

4.2.1. Channels and materials

As stated in the previous section, MiniStor will use a balance mix of traditional (printed dissemination materials, participation to events, scientific publications) and due to the current pandemic, a strong online presence (via social media website, material published on other websites and online events). All materials, for communication or dissemination purposes, will be adjusted to each stakeholder groups and will be regularly analyzed and adapted as see fit by each project partner.

The table below shows the correlation between the communication channels identified and the specific materials to be distributed through them:

Actions	Activity	Channel
Publications	Non-scientific Publications General Articles	Press releases e-Newsletter News sites articles Blogs
Events (project and external)	Events for the general public	Public Presentations Networking
Online	Online communication	MiniStor website* Social media Online events
Meetings with stakeholders, policy makers, other project representatives	Face-to-face or online meetings with stakeholders	Policy briefs Minutes Promotional materials
Media	Mass media campaigns	Press releases Articles Media Kit
Communication Materials	Promotional material	Project Videos Infographics Newsletters

		Roll up and poster Brochure Materials (pen, bags, folders)
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Table 3. Correlation between the communication channels and specific materials

*Already existing networks: from other project partners, associations, platforms, other projects or initiatives to which members belong and that can act as channels for sharing project activities.

Dissemination activities refer to the public disclosure of results to a specific and specialized audience (scientific communities, industry stakeholders...) using a scientific language and via specific channels as described below:

Actions	Activity	Channel
Publications (online and printed)	Scientific publications	Articles in scientific magazines, journal, research social networks (research gate) and blogs
Events (project and external)	Presentations in scientific conferences Stakeholders events Conferences proceedings	Presentations of project outcomes Dissemination materials
Online	Online disclosure of results	Project Website (Knowledge centre) Social Media Deliverables
Pilot visits	Stakeholders engagement	Dissemination materials
Meetings with stakeholders, policy makers, other project representatives	Stakeholders engagement	Online repository of results Minutes Dissemination materials
Media	Mass media dissemination	Conference proceedings Press Releases Media kit
Dissemination Materials	Results-oriented material	Project Videos Infographics Newsletters Brochure of results Scientific posters

Table 4. Correlation between the dissemination channels and specific materials

4.2.2. MiniStor Communication and Dissemination Materials

FEUGA, as WP8 leader, is responsible for the creation of the communication and dissemination materials. The materials will be adapted by the WPL as requested by each project partner to better reach out to each stakeholder group. The main materials to be used for creating and strengthening the MiniStor brand are:

- **Brochure**, for general communication of the project targets and showing the main objectives, expected outcomes, partners and regions involved. Brochures should be displayed at events to which stakeholders are attending to present the project and generate interest in its development and results. Additional brochures will be created to adapt to the availability of results. MiniStor first brochure was available at M6⁴.

⁴ http://ministor.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/Brochure_Ministor_04.20-web.pdf

WHAT IS MINISTOR?

MiniStor (Minimal Size Thermal and Electrical Energy Storage System for In-Situ Residential Installation) is a project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

The MiniStor project aims at designing and producing a novel compact integrated thermal storage system for achieving sustainable heating, cooling and electricity storage that can be adapted to new and existing systems in residential buildings.

Eighteen partners across the European Union, Switzerland and the UK work together to harness the large potential of EU buildings to increase its energy efficiency performance by providing a new and innovative solution. MiniStor system optimizes the use and management of thermal energy by allowing it to be stored, levelling demand peaks and increasing the use of renewables affected by intermittency such as solar-based heating.

The MiniStor system is to be demonstrated and validated in five demonstration sites located in Ireland, France, Greece and Hungary to test its effectiveness at different local climatic conditions, facilitating market replication while offering an innovative, efficient and clean thermal and electrical energy storage solution for all Europeans.

WHAT DO WE DO?

The MiniStor concept will be demonstrated and evaluated in an operational environment of real-life conditions in one pre-pilot and five demonstration sites, following appropriate deployment guidelines and legislations. The demonstration sites are located in North-West Europe (Ireland), Western Europe (France), Southern Europe (Greece) and Central Europe (Hungary). These pilot sites represent residential usage having diverse climatic conditions, thermal load needs, energy realities, expectations and regulations.

Deployment in these demonstration sites will be thoroughly planned, their stakeholders will be trained to maximise use of the MiniStor system. Acceptance tests of the system will be performed, allowing to validate the human-centric HEMS (Home Energy Management System) pre views to installation.

KEEP IN TOUCH WITH MINISTOR

Progress and results of MiniStor will be available to researchers, academics, industry stakeholders and users, among others. Different dissemination activities and materials will be provided such as latest news, technical articles, handbooks, newsletters and many more!

Keep an eye on the project's website and do not miss out on all the resources this project has to offer. Do not forget to follow MiniStor on social networks.

www.ministor.eu
info@ministor.eu
@MiniStorH2020

ENERGY EFFICIENCY INNOVATION AT HOME

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869821.

MiniStor system: Sustainability made minimal size

The MiniStor thermal storage system is based on a high-performing thermochemical material (TCM) reaction, combined with hot and latent heat storage based on phase-change materials (PCM). The electrical storage is a conventional system based on a Li-ion battery for flexibility and usage year-round. The storage system allows for compact storing of RES-based energy using hybrid photovoltaic thermal panels (PVT).

This system includes a home energy management system (HEMS) that connects to the Internet of Things (IoT) to synchronise and efficiently manage the overall supply and demand at household level, responding for grid constraints and price signals.

The MiniStor system provides stability, performance and usage of at least 20 years with a minimal-size. The estimated storage volume will be 0.72 m³. The overall system storage density is extremely high, up to 10.6 times higher than water-based storage systems for an operating heating temperature difference in the range of 15°C (around 182 kWh/m³). This system reduces the net energy consumption of a building by at least 44%, and will have an expected return-on-investment period of 6.7 years.

MiniStor integrated storage system concept

The MiniStor system is to be demonstrated and validated in five demonstration sites located in Ireland, France, Greece and Hungary.

WHY MINISTOR?

1. Innovative and minimal-size storage solution for heating and new residential buildings
2. Thermal storage for both heating and cooling throughout the year
3. Electrical energy storage and management to increase profitability
4. Consumer at the heart of MiniStor: Efficiency and user comfort
5. Reduction of the building's net energy consumption by at least 44%
6. Return on investment period of 6.7 years

OUR IMPACT

- Minimal size energy storage solution
- Long-term energy security
- Minimal environmental impact
- Towards a decarbonised EU building stock
- Support Europe's Energy Policy for a sustainable energy market

Figure 11. MiniStor Brochure

- **Poster/Roll-up:** for increasing the visibility of both the project and its partners. Posters have been produced to be used in the activities developed by MiniStor partners and strengthen the corporate identity of the project. These roll-ups and posters can be adapted upon partners request to fit the topic of an event or any other specific need.

Figure 12. Example of MiniStor Posters

- **Power point presentation:** updated regularly. They should be used in conferences and external events where partners are participating and should help them explain the project and how it is developing.
- **Promotional materials:** such as bags, pens, folders with MiniStor visual identity can be produced, if necessary, to increase the engagement of stakeholders with the project during events and meetings. Other promotional material can be produced upon partner’s requests.
- **Policy briefs:** a policy brief is a concise summary of a particular issue, the policy options to deal with it, and some recommendations on the best option. It is aimed at policymakers and other stakeholders that have the potential to influence on policy and regulation. These will be available on MiniStor website and ca be also distributed on events and meetings with stakeholders.
- **Infographics:** an infographic is a form of visual communication meant to capture attention and enhance comprehension. In this era, “infographic” has become the broadest descriptor of a specific type of visual communication that includes graphics showing data, copy, or both. FEUGA will create infographics with general information about the project that can be used online or in a printed version for events and meetings with stakeholders. Partners are welcome to suggest ideas for infographics depending on their needs.

Figure 13. Example of MiniStor Infographic

- Videos:** FEUGA will create two general videos. One at the beginning of the project and one towards the end. Apart from these two materials, FEUGA will create short videos over the project development that will be disseminated through social media, in order to ensure the visibility of the project. For that, partners may be asked for raw footage and audio-visual resources. These videos can be used online or presented during events and meetings with stakeholders. Partners are welcome to suggest ideas for short videos depending on their needs⁵.

⁵ MiniStor Project video: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DvF-Nb9_Xpk&feature=emb_logo

Figure 14. MiniStor Video screenshot

- Newsletters:** FEUGA will produce at least two newsletters per year. FEUGA will request information to partners. Partners are requested to share MiniStor newsletter through their networks. MiniStor newsletter will be available on MiniStor website and disseminated through social media. No contact lists will be created for the distribution of the newsletter to avoid any possible non-compliance with the GDPR ruling⁶.

Figure 15. MiniStor newsletter

⁶ First MiniStor Newsletter:

http://x5smx.mjt.lu/nl2/x5smx/xuuv.html?m=AG4AAEFy9agAAAAAAAAAAAC_xlMAAAANuQAAAAABFY8QBfPopuG6mUYnRSSO6uDnsdn9oi6wARbsE&b=4a409c7e&e=c827e75f&x=y-EwCP3bgmaSABQxn6Bhjq

4.3. MiniStor Online presence

Two documents were available on Microsoft Teams early on (M3) ‘A Communication Strategy’ (Appendix) and ‘Social Media Guidelines’ (Appendix) to offer a base for all members of the consortium to learn how to navigate the online presence of MiniStor.

MiniStor project has a constant online presence through the maintenance and animation of the MiniStor website and its social media networks (twitter and LinkedIn) that will complement each other. Additional external presence will be provided by the participation in external events (due to the covid-19 situation) and those publications and general articles published on online media.

The participation in other social media networks, such as ResearchGate or Academic.edu will be analyzed depending on the availability of results. More channels can be added during the development of the project depending on partner’s requests and stakeholders needs. All channels are managed by FEUGA with the support of all consortium partners.

4.3.1. MiniStor Website (<https://ministor.eu/>)

The MiniStor website is accessible at <https://ministor.eu/> and will be the main communication tool for disseminate information related to the project. The MiniStor website will become a single gateway to access available results for people seeking information.

The website will incorporate basic project information, key results, news items, event alerts, and it will also offer added-value services such as publications, newsletter, as well as signpost to related news, events and projects. The website is foreseen to be accessible and easy-to-use, empowered by social features to trigger communication among stakeholders, with special focus on interested parties from the energy and residential sectors, with links to the project’s social media, and/or other communication options, facilitating thus, the exchange of information amongst project partners, stakeholders and wider public.

The main sections of the project website include the following:

- HOME: relevant information regarding the project, its development, and the consortium.
- MiniStor: Consortium information, general information, objectives, demonstration sites.
- OUR WORK: Explanation of the project's work plan in a language that is both informative and understandable to the general public. Special attention will be focused on the demo sites to be developed for validating the MiniStor system.
- KNOWLEDGE CENTRE: Specific information about the heating system, data gathering, demonstration activities, etc. All results and project advancements are available in this page and will be regularly updated.
 - Scientific Publications
 - Factsheets/Infographics
 - Video
 - Training sessions
 - Workshops
 - Communication materials
 - Public deliverables
- NEWS AND EVENTS: Project-related news. All relevant information regarding the progress of the project as well as related topics of interest.

- RELATED LINKS: Links to other projects, initiatives, associations or entities that have to do with the MiniStor project.
- CONTACT: Details on how to get in contact with the MiniStor project consortium. Contact form. A specific e-mail has been created for such purpose: info@ministor.eu

Get encouraged and **trained with MiniStor**

Access our trainings and latest discoveries!

Figure 16. MiniStor website

4.3.2. MiniStor Social Media: LinkedIn

Access: MiniStorH2020 <https://www.linkedin.com/company/38098733>

LinkedIn is a business-oriented professional networking tool that is used by many as a source of information and inspiration, therefore a solid presence to amplify the news on the website is necessary. It therefore constitutes an important platform for discussions, relevant to LinkedIn account, among experts in the area and various stakeholders in general.

MiniStor maintains a LinkedIn company page, making it possible to connect to very relevant professionals and disseminate to them our main news and developments. On the other hand, it gives the possibility to subscribe and post on the relevant major groups relevant to the fields of the project. All posts are thought with not only attractive information but also visual catching banners maintaining the visual identity of MiniStor. MiniStor LinkedIn account currently has 89 followers.

Figure 17. MiniStor LinkedIn account

4.3.1. MiniStor Social Media: Twitter

Access: @MiniStorH2020 <https://twitter.com/MiniStorH2020>

As a rapid and professional communication tool, Twitter allows real-time interactions and very high potential outreach towards MiniStor's target audience, using hashtags and thematic tweets. MiniStor

already has an active Twitter account (@MiniStorH2020) and has chosen the following hashtags for its tweets:

#MiniStor #EnergyStorage #sustainableheating #sustainablecooling #residential #climatechange #energyefficiency #sustainability #innovation #H2020 #Horizon2020 #research

The twitter account has been used for promoting and disseminating the MiniStor developments, news, events, outcomes, etc. Moreover, re-tweets are made of relevant and interesting content from diverse sources. Finally, through targeted following of other relevant users MiniStor not only gets access to more relevant content and updates, but also acquires more followers.

As a Horizon2020 project, MiniStor follows the official Twitter account for the Horizon 2020 programme @EU_H2020 thus becoming a part of the community of H2020 projects on social media. Following the guidelines received from the EC, we pursue to use a hashtag #H2020 and tag @EU_H2020 whenever announcing important news which clearly shows the real impact of our research.

Since MiniStor account was launched in March 2020, the project's Twitter activities have led to 287 followers (which are in turn followed by thousands of followers). The total number of earned impressions is 12.1K over the last 28-day period. Many of the project's tweets have been re-tweeted and reached by large audiences through the followers of the users that re-tweeted them.

Figure 18. MiniStor Twitter account

4.3.2. MiniStor Social Media: YouTube and other networks

Access: MiniStor H2020 <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCjfUgKd4apmTTWvgrD5-XmQ?>

MiniStor has a YouTube channel where currently the first project video is hosted. Additional audiovisual materials will be upload as results become available.

Figure 19. YouTube Channels

Significant project developments, news and announcements, press releases, but also articles introducing MiniStor and presenting the developments of the project will be published in other online sources, including the professional specialized platforms, Cordis, relevant thematic blogs/collaboration platforms, partners' web portals, as well as through several freely accessible tools.

The participation in other social media networks, such as ResearchGate or Academic.edu will be analyzed depending on the availability of results. More channels can be added during the development of the project depending on partner's requests and stakeholders needs. All channels are managed by FEUGA with the support of all consortium partners.

4.3.3. Dissemination oriented channels: Events

MiniStor awareness-raising campaigns will focus mainly on events. Events are important means for MiniStor to communicate and disseminate its work. Events are often an effective way to engage relevant EU affairs press representatives to ensure a coverage at the EU level.

As per project requirements, is MiniStor is expected to be involved in a variety of event, ranging from local events, events organized by collaborating EU projects, to EU and International conferences and workshops. This includes as well taking on tasks related to event planning, implementation and support i.e. with communication materials (brochures, posters, etc.).

MiniStor's participation in events is also an opportunity to increase and strengthen the project's network with relevant parties and potential multipliers. MiniStor's representation in events can take place in different ways, including paper or project presentations, poster presentations and/or attendance for networking purposes. Project promotional materials such as brochures and a poster (where relevant) will be also used for dissemination purposes.

A Google Drive sheet listing potential events for consortium partners (MiniStor Tracker⁷) has been created to keep track of the partners' participation and facilitate its report and follow up.

⁷ MiniStor Tracker:
https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1luFLVL7aYpzoMV5NOnuRUWPJZakNpKW_2MXm7aZQGNy/edit#gid=541890420

Events and workshops All types of events → This includes external events and events organized by members of the consortium

TITLE OF THE PROJECT: MiniStor
 RESPONSIBLE FOR THE TASK: All partners
 TASK: Events participation and organization
 LAST UPDATE: 06/04/20

EVENT NUMBER	PARTNER	ABOUT THE EVENT			
		TITLE OF THE EVENT	TYPE OF EVENT	STATUS	DATE OF THE EVENT
1	FEUGA	ustainable Places 2022	icipation to a Confer	Will attend	29/10/2020
2	IERC	ustainable Places 2022	icipation to a Confer	Will attend	29/10/2020
3	HSLU	sobre thermal energy	icipation to a Confer	Attended	
4	HSLU	sobre thermal energy	icipation to a Confer	Will attend	
5	HSLU	CISBAT 2021	nisation of a Confer	Will attend	

Figure 20. MiniStor Tracker

The level of involvement in events will vary, according to the nature and interest of the event. A thorough procedure for deciding on MiniStor’s participation on dissemination activities will be followed, to identify those events which are "tailored" to promote the project. The final list of events will be discussed in terms of cost efficiency, input to the promotion and awareness strategy and will be updated accordingly. After each event, the concerned MiniStor partner is requested to update its participation on the dedicated Google Drive sheet with all the relevant information about the event. Due to the current pandemic, numerous events have been cancelled and postponed, therefore, completing an initial dissemination of the project. The consortium expects that as soon the current situation improves; more project results will be available to make an effective dissemination of the project outcomes.

4.3.1. Dissemination oriented channels: Publications

Publications in journals and conferences are a conventional and effective way to disseminate project outcomes and attract the attention of scientific, business and public stakeholders.

MiniStor’s initial target includes at least 10 publications in international journals and papers presented in scientific conferences and workshops. Scientific dissemination will be taken care of mainly by research partners. To support this activity, publications will be also featured on MiniStor’s website. Project partners already have an excellent track record on high-standard peer-reviewed scientific publications. The consortium will participate to the Open Research Data programme as it strongly believes that the sharing of the information gathered during the project can allow a better understanding of energy efficiency in buildings market challenges and thus improving scientific knowledge. For scientific publications, the ‘golden’ open access model will be chosen, preferable in a fast-moving scientific field. All scientific publications will either be deposited via OpenAIRE in the lead authors’ institutions repository, or, if such a repository does not exist, in the centralized, EC supported, Zenodo repository. MiniStor beneficiaries will also check that publication metadata is adequate for EU funded projects⁵⁰.

underlying data will be made available as supplemental information, in a thematic repository or Zenodo, and mentioned in the main text of the publication. An additional advantage of the golden open access approach is that publications will be available for other MiniStor dissemination activities. Details will be included in the DMP, which will be updated throughout the project’s lifetime.

In order to keep track on the project partners’ submissions and publications, the MiniStor Tracker has been created. Project partners will be asked to fill in the information in the Google Drive table each time they submit relevant publications to scientific journals/magazines.

Relevant Publications	Type	Link
Energy Storage Journal	Journal	http://www.energystoragejournal.com/
MDPI	Journal	https://www.mdpi.com/
The Journal of Energy Storage	Journal	https://www.researchgate.net/journal/2352-152X-The-Journal-of-Energy-Storage
PV Magazine	Magazine	https://www.pv-magazine.com/
Energy News	Magazine	https://www.energy-storage.news/
Energética21	Magazine	http://www.energetica21.com/articulos-y-entrevistas/almacenamiento-energetico
Energías Renovables	Magazine	https://www.energias-renovables.com/almacenamiento/como-avanza-el-almacenamiento-energetico-20200422
Revista Energía	Magazine	https://www.revistaenergia.com/13546/
E&T Energy and Technology	Magazine	https://eandt.theiet.org/tags/energy-storage
Journal of Energy Storage - Scimago	Journal	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100400826&tip=sid&clean=0

Table 5. Example of list of possible magazines and journal where MiniStor can be portrayed.

4.3.2. Media kit

FEUGA has produced a document to facilitate the presentation of the project and its progress to media (Media-kit available in the appendix). It should be used by partners to draw media attention to the project and its activities and invite them to MiniStor events. It should be updated regularly during the project. The document is sent in English, and partners are welcome to translate it and adapt it to their regional/national language and specificities, if they wish to do so. This document presents the project in a clear language, easy to understand for those not familiarized with the project’s topic.

Figure 21. MiniStor Media Kit

4.4. Key performance indicators (KPIs)

The evaluation of the communication strategy concerns both qualitative and quantitative indicators. Once measurable objectives are defined, the process of evaluation will involve examining the progress of the strategy’s implementation and will refer to an outreach activity that is quantifiable through the attendance of persons present from the audiences, quantity of material distributed, number of events participated, the development and dissemination of messages and materials, media presence and traffic created in social media, among others.

In order to measure the impact of the conducted activities and to be able to adjust the dissemination strategy for achieving the expected outcomes and maximizing visibility, a set of initial metrics has been developed. Such metrics will allow having a regular update on the amount and the effectiveness of the activities conducted. The tables below present the expected outcomes for each type of the activities:

4.4.1. Communication KPIs

The communication activities of Horizon 2020 projects go beyond dissemination: they do not involve project results only but also the project in general such as the societal challenges or European added value of the project. Thus, communication activities target a much wider audience, including the media and the general public. It is important to use a less technical language so that a non-specialist audience can easily understand the goals and means of the project.

Channel / activity	Key performance indicators (KPI)	Common objectives
MiniStor website	N° of visitors	1000 visitors /month in the last year of the project Pending
	Time of visit	with +2 min staying Pending
	N° of news	at least 50 news accumulated. 8 news published
MiniStor Social Media	N° of followers (Twitter)	At least 700 followers 325 followers so far
	N° of followers (LinkedIn)	200 followers 89 followers so far
YouTube	N° of visits	1000 per video 122 accumulated so far
Press releases	N° of press releases	2 per project partner Pending
Partners’ existing Communication channels	N° of audience members reached	To reach an audience of more than 40,000 people (17 partners) Pending
Leaflet	N° of Leaflets distributed	50000 Pending
Newsletters	N° of newsletters	2 per year 1 published M10 1 scheduled M14
Videos	N° of promotional videos	2 1 done by M10 1 planned M48

Table 6. Communication KPIs

4.4.2. Dissemination KPIS

Dissemination aims at maximizing the impact of research results in the public domain. Therefore, the target audience of dissemination activities is any potential user of the project results: the scientific community, stakeholders, industry, policy makers, investors, etc. Due to the current pandemic the dissemination KPIs may be remodeled to accommodate online event formats and other activities that may be equal in terms of impact.

Channel / activity	Key performance indicators (KPI)		Common objectives
Stakeholders & mid-term workshop, National workshops	400 stakeholders approx. attending project's events	N° of attendees	50 per workshop Pending
Final Conference		N° of attendees	100 Final Conference Pending
Demonstration workshops	N° of Demonstration workshops		3 / 50 stakeholders each Pending
Dissemination workshops	N° of dissemination workshops		3 / 50 stakeholders each 1 direct link to EC policy Pending
Participation in events	N° of international events		At least 2 per partner after 2nd year Pending
	N° of national conference		2 national conferences per partner Pending
Infographics	Per pilot site		5 1 general infographic done
Articles	N° of articles in sector-specific magazines		1 publication/year per partner Pending
Scientific Publications	N° of published publication		+10 published articles (at least 1 per technical WP, open-access prioritized) Pending
Clustering with other projects/entities	N° of Joint actions		At least 10 joint actions within identified networks and other H2020 projects. Pending
Policy Briefs	N° of policy briefs		3 Pending

Table 7. Dissemination KPIs

4.5. Monitoring and reporting tools

This communication and dissemination plan (M1-M12) involves (partly) the first phase of the project’s communication and dissemination strategy, for which awareness raising is the main objective. During this period fundamental channels, materials and documents have been created to serve as the basis of the overall activities throughout the project, as described in the previous section of this document. It is expected to have a substantial increase in activities during the second phase, as project results will start to become available.

The major dissemination and communication activities scheduled for the project course, apart from those covered by the KPIs (previous session) are listed below:

Type	Description	Time	Involvement	Status
MiniStor logo	The MiniStor logo has been designed and will be used in all documents and publications of the project	M2	FEUGA	Completed
MiniStor Book of Style	The visual identity of the project is defined	M3	FEUGA	Completed
Twitter account	Create a Twitter Account for disseminating project news & developments	M3	FEUGA	Completed Regular updated
LinkedIn page	Create a LinkedIn page for engaging various stakeholders and disseminating projects news & developments to professional public	M3	FEUGA	Completed Regular updated
MiniStor Social Media Guidelines	Guidelines and instructions for consortium partners about MiniStor’s social media presence	M3	FEUGA	Completed
MiniStor PowerPoint template	Template to be used for the project presentations	M3	FEUGA	Completed
MiniStor website	The online presence of MiniStor	M6	FEUGA	Completed, Regular updated
Project brochure – initial version	Designing of a brochure for promoting the project in various local and EU/International events	M7	FEUGA	Completed

Updated project brochure	Updated project brochure including key project outcomes mid-project	M27	FEUGA	Pending
Project poster/roll-up – initial version	Designing of a poster for promoting the project in various events. A poster template can also serve as a basis for creation of new posters with updated content depending on the needs of an event	M10	FEUGA	Completed
Updated project poster/roll-up	Updated project poster including key project outcomes mid-project	M27	FEUGA	Pending
Press Releases	6 versions focusing on the project presentations and outcomes	M1- M54	all partners	Continuous
Publications	A significant number of publications are expected both in conferences and in journals	M1 – M54	All partners	Continuous
Events’ participation	Participation in events (i.e. conferences, workshops, local events) in order to raise awareness about MiniStor and disseminate the project’s results	M1 – M54	All partners	Continuous
MiniStor mid-project workshops	Organization of the mid-project workshop	M54	FEUGA All partners	Pending
MiniStor final workshop	Organization of the final workshop	M33 – M54	FEUGA All partners	Pending
Newsletter	Project news, achievements and events, in the form of a Newsletter	M1 – M54	FEUGA All partners	Continuous
Blog Posts	Articles introducing MiniStor will be also published on third parties’ portals	M1- M54	FEUGA All partners	Continuous
Innovation factsheets and infographics	Creation of a one-page leaflet, including information on the project outcomes per demonstration site	M1 – M54	FEUGA All partners	Pending
Videos	Producing videos creating awareness on the project development	M1- M54	FEUGA All partners	Continuous
Liaise with other projects/initiatives	Collaboration for mutual dissemination and knowledge exchange with other relevant projects & initiatives	M1- M54	FEUGA All partners	Continuous
Standardisation activities	Follow-up on preparing and providing the project’s contributions to policies	M12- M54	FEUGA All partners	Continuous
On-site demonstrations.	Demonstrate the MiniStor system	M33 – M54		Pending

Table 8. Activities additional to KPIs reported and planned, including the partner’s involvement and timeframe

As mentioned earlier, a monitoring tool has been developed to monitor and assess the dissemination and communication activities implemented in the project. This is based on a set of KPIs that covers all the aspects of the dissemination and communication strategy. This monitoring tool will be modified upon request of the partners to fit their needs and the projects.

The tracker currently includes information about publications and events but it will be updated accordingly to the KPIs approved by the consortium⁸:

Events and workshops All types of events → This includes external events and events organized by members of the consortium

TITLE OF THE PROJECT: MiniStor
 RESPONSIBLE FOR THE TASK: All partners
 TASK: Events participation and organization
 LAST UPDATE: 06/04/20

EVENT NUMBER	PARTNER	ABOUT THE EVENT			
		TITLE OF THE EVENT	TYPE OF EVENT	STATUS	DATE OF THE EVENT
1	FEUGA	ustainable Places 2020	icipation to a Confer	Will attend	29/10/2020
2	IERC	ustainable Places 2020	icipation to a Confer	Will attend	29/10/2020
3	HSLU	sobre thermal energy	icipation to a Confer	Attended	
4	HSLU	sobre thermal energy	icipation to a Confer	Will attend	
5	HSLU	CISBAT 2021	nisation of a Confer	Will attend	

COMMUNICATION KPIs PARTNERS INVOLVED ALL

Short explanatory note: The communication activities of Horizon 2020 projects go beyond dissemination: they do not involve project results only but also the project in general such as the societal challenges or European added-value of the project. Thus, communication activities target a much wider audience, including the media and the general public. It is important to use a less technical language so that a non-specialist audience can easily understand the goals and means of the project.

Channel / activity	performance indicators (Common objectives	
MiniStor website	Nº of visitors	1000 visitors /month in the last year of the project	
	Time of visit	with +2 min staying	
MiniStor Social Media	Nº of news	at least 50 news accumulated.	7 done
MiniStor Social Media	Nº of followers (Twitter)	At least 700 followers	204 Followers
	Nº of followers (LinkedIn)	200 followers	77 followers
Youtube	Nº of visits	1000 per video	53 first video
Press releases	Nº of press releases	2 per project partner	0
Partners' existing communication channels		To reach an audience of more than 40,000 people (17 partners).	reporting needed
Leaflet	Nº of leaflets distributed	50000	reporting needed

Figure 22. MiniStor Tracker screenshots

⁸ MiniStor Tracker: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1luFLVL7aYpzoMV5NOnuRUWPJZakNpKW_2MXm7aZQGNy/edit?usp=sharing

5. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable outlines MiniStor’s plan for communication and dissemination activities to be carried out during the development of the project and ensure the impact of its results beyond the project’s lifetime. This plan is a ‘living document’ that will be updated as the project develops to offer guidance and a base regarding the communication and dissemination efforts carried out by the consortium.

In this document, the overall objectives and purpose of the communication and dissemination plan are defined together with the general background of the WP8 and the plan itself. This deliverable covers the fundamental objectives, target audience, key messages and channels of the plan for the specific materials and configuration of the online and physical presence of the project. As well, key performance indicators, reported activities, milestones and the monitoring and reporting tools set for this project are described.

MiniStor visual identity is described in this plan (section 3) and in the appendix (MiniStor book of style) based on the different versions of the MiniStor main logo and its co-existence with the EU emblem. The project’s specific typography and corporate colors are well-described configuring the entire MiniStor brand and the guidelines to maintain it in a consistent manner. In the offset of the project, templates were made available following the visual identity of the project, namely, the following templates for: deliverables, agendas, power point presentations, list of attendees and letters.

The MiniStor communication and dissemination plan was structured to address a full range of potential actors playing different but fundamental roles in the areas of interest for the project. Objectives were defined specifically for communication activities and the dissemination ones. As the results of the project and its activities will increase over time, the MiniStor communication and dissemination approach is based in five main phases that can be adapted as they are subjected to the availability of results and stakeholder engagement opportunities: the initial awareness phase (M1-M14), the strategic dissemination phase (M14-M26), the mid-project results oriented dissemination (M26-M30), the second strategic dissemination phase (M30-M42), and finally the final results exploitation phase (M42-M54). As said, the final goal of these phases is to structure the efforts based on the availability of results, therefore, these phases will fluctuate alongside the development of the rest of the work packages.

The target audiences identified cover broadly three main stakeholder groups: policy-makers, the residential sector and the wider research community. Due to the heterogeneous nature of these targeted audiences, communication and dissemination activities are planned to be adapted accordingly and through the most effective channels. This plan covers key and tailor-made messages for each specific target group together with the most recommended channels (press releases, e-newsletters, news, articles, blogs, public presentations, networking activities, social media and events, among others). The channels, actions and activities are well-distinguished to be adapted to either communication or dissemination goals.

For the purpose of an effective communication and dissemination, materials have been created as it is the case of the project brochures, posters and roll-ups, a power point presentations, policy briefs, infographics, project videos and newsletters. Other materials can be created depending on the needs of each stakeholder group.

Following the communication and dissemination plan, MiniStor has a constant online presence, ever so needed in the current pandemic situation. The MiniStor online presence is structured through its dedicated website, as the center of all actions and a repository of all project developments, social media

networks (twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube). Other social networks will be considered as results become available. As dissemination oriented channels: events and publications were identified as two priority actions. In order to facilitate the understanding of the project, mainly addressing the media, a MiniStor Media-kit was created (appendix).

In terms of the evaluation of the communication and dissemination plan and to take the necessary contingency measures to achieve the desired project impact, a series of key performance indicators were created and agreed upon with the members of the consortium. Two lists of KPIs were created to cover the communication activities on one side and dissemination on the other.

Regarding the tracking and reporting actions, an online tool was made available under the name 'MiniStor Tracker' for consortium partners to report their activities and jointly follow up the development and compliance with the communication and dissemination plan.

This deliverable (D8.1) includes the communication and dissemination plan created by FEUGA with the contribution of all consortium partners since the onset of the project. A formal update of the deliverable will be provided mid-project to be aligned with the first draft of the PEDR. At the end of the project, a final version will be presented (D8.2) in coordination with the final PEDR, together with the products and results of each communication and dissemination activity, reporting as well future-oriented dissemination and communication activities, foreseen by each project partner and the work package leader, to ensure the continuation of the project's impact beyond its lifetime.

6. Appendix

- **MiniStor Book of Style (14/01/2020)**
- **MiniStor Social Media Guidelines (24/04/2020)**
- **MiniStor Communication strategy (24/04/2020)**
- **MiniStor Media-kit (25/10/2020)**

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BRAND MANUAL

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MiniStor

Visual identity guide

MiniStor BRAND MANUAL

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INTRODUCTION

Consumers often think that a branded article is preferable to a generic one, even though they both look alike. But, what is a brand? A Brand is the way, in this case, a European Project is perceived by those who experience it. More than a name, a design or a symbol, a brand is the recognizable face of the Project. Branding helps to identify a Project and distinguish it from other initiatives. The most important reason why branding is important is because it is how a Project gets recognition. A name, visual identity, a recognized brand can elevate the perceived quality of a Project.

Visual identity is one of the most important aspects of the brand. The care, normalization and homogenization of the visual identity of our project will allow us among other aspects:

- Promote stakeholder recognition
- Enhance credibility in the project's actions and results
- Ensure quality and reliability of the project
- Inspire a sense of belonging to a group with shared values

Given this scenario, we need to be aware of the need to care for the brand, and by extension, the visual identity of the project. These indications are a tool to achieve excellence in the use of your brand: MiniStor, avoiding deviations in the different uses.

CORPORATE LOGO

The MiniStor Masterbrand or Corporate Logo comprises two elements: the logo symbol and logo type.

The use of any stylized, animated, hand drawn or other versions of an unofficial logo is not permitted. This would undermine the logo system and brand consistency.

The principal logo to use is the Full Logotype. Other versions are reserved only when the background of the page forces a different version, this is, black or negative backgrounds.

The EU Emblem will be located on the left of the full logotype always ensuring both the MiniStor logo and EU Emblem are equal.

Recommended formats are:
.eps | .ai | .png | .jpg | .tiff

Full Logotype

Master Brand

Logo Symbol

Logo Type

Logo Versions

COLOR

NEGATIVE COLOR

BLACK

NEGATIVE BLACK

Co-existence with UE brand

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Logo Backgrounds

CORPORATE GRADIENT BACKGROUND

BLACK BACKGROUND

DARK IMAGE BACKGROUND

CLEAR IMAGE BACKGROUND

Incorrect logo applications

PLEASE READ CAREFULLY THE DON'TS

1. Do not invert the logo symbol.
2. Do not alter the logo symbol.
3. Do not alter the logo type style.
4. Do not change the size relationship between the logo symbol and logo type.
5. Do not use different color versions than those contained in the brand manual.
6. Never change the proportions of the logo vertically or horizontally or alter the appearance in any way.

LOGO CONSTRUCTION, CLEARSPACE AND MINIMUM LOGO SIZES

It is important to keep corporate marks clear of any other graphic elements.

To regulate this, an exclusion zone has been established around the corporate mark (m). This exclusion zone indicates the closest any other graphic element or message can be positioned in relation to the mark of the symbol itself and our project name. They have a fixed relationship that should never be changed in any way.

Clearspace & construction

Minimum logo sizes

FULL LOGO SIZES

Minimum size:
10 mm x 8.493 mm

10 mm.

LOGO SYMBOL

Minimum size:
8 mm x 4.982 mm

8 mm.

CORPORATE COLOR SYSTEM

Primary Color System

Color plays an important role in the MiniStor corporate identity program. The palette of primary colors below has been developed, which comprise the "One Voice" color scheme.

A consistent use of these colors will contribute to the cohesive and harmonious look of the brand's identity. Check with your designer or printer when using the corporate colors to ensure they are consistent.

Gradient Blue-Red

COLOR CODES

CMYK : C081 M002 Y011 K000
Pantone : 638 C
RGB : R000 G173 B216
Web : #00acd7

COLOR CODES

CMYK : C000 M083 Y073 K000
Pantone : Warm RedC
RGB : R233 G071 B063
Web : #e8473e

Secondary Colorsystem

The Secondary colors are complementary to our official colors, but are not recognizable identifiers for MiniStor. Use them to accent and support the primary color palette.

Black

COLOR CODES

CMYK : C000 M000 Y000 K100
Pantone : Neutral BlackC
RGB : R000 G000 B000
Web : #000000

White

COLOR CODES

CMYK : C000 M000 Y000 K000
Pantone : White
RGB : R255 G255 B255
Web : #ffffff

Grey

COLOR CODES

CMYK : C017 M000 Y000 K050
Pantone : 443C
RGB : R135 G148 B155
Web : #87949b

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Social Media Guidelines

(INFORMATION FOR PARTNERS ONLY)

SHORT INTRODUCTION TO MINISTOR SOCIAL MEDIA NETWORKS

The MiniStor project is present in several social media networks. General Social Media are Twitter, LinkedIn and youtube, as for the more academics ones, Academia.eu and ResearchGate. More channels can be added during the development of the project depending on partners requests and stakeholders needs. It is included here as well, MiniStor website, event though is not a social media channel, it offers all the information that will be after replicated through social media. All channels are managed by FEUGA with the support of all consortium partners.

How can you find MiniStor channels?

Social Media Channels	Link	Social Media Channels	Link
Twitter	<u>Account:</u> @MiniStorH2020 <u>Hashtag:</u> #MiniStor #MiniStorH2020 <u>Link:</u> here	Academia.eu	To be assessed as results are available
LinkedIn	<u>Account:</u> MiniStorH2020 <u>Hashtag:</u> #MiniStor #MiniStorH2020 <u>Link</u> here	ResearchGate	To be assessed as results are available

How and what can be published on MiniStor channels?

Website http://ministor.eu/	Published Content:	(Mainly related to MiniStor) Information and news about the project, its progress and results; project articles, publications, public deliverables, other projects and links and own project events (or with MiniStor presence).
	How to publish your content on the website:	Send news items/events/articles and others to Inés Arias at iaras@feuga.es . Unedited information can be also sent, and it will be given the correct format.

Twitter @MiniStorH2020	Published Content:	(Related to MiniStor, other projects and activities about MiniStor subject) Information and news about the project, its progress and results; articles related to MiniStor subject; links, other projects and initiatives and websites of interest to the stakeholders.
	How to publish your content on the website:	1) Send news items/events or unedited information to Inés Arias at iarias@feuga.es 2) Publish a tweet on your own account making sure to tag MiniStor account (@MiniStorH2020) and to use the hashtag #MiniStor and/or #MiniStorH2020
LinkedIn MiniStorH2020	Published Content:	(Mainly related to MiniStor) Information regarding the project and its development and results: consortium meetings; design, building and operation of pilot plants; results; presence at external events, etc.
	How to publish your content on the website:	1) Send news items/events or unedited information to Inés Arias at iarias@feuga.es 2) Publish the post on your own account making sure to tag IMPAQT's account and use the dedicated hashtag #aquaculture.

Youtube, Academia.eu, ResearchGate are pending

We kindly ask all partners to please send news items regularly to keep social media networks dynamic and to please share the information published (posts/tweets) on your own networks to increase reachability as much as possible.

What can FEUGA do for you in terms of Social Media?

- ⇒ Publish content in all channels
- ⇒ Draft articles and news items from unedited information.
- ⇒ Promote MiniStor events and events where MiniStor partners are attending.
- ⇒ Overall media coverage of Project Meetings and events.
- ⇒ Visibility of project's results, activities and progress.

Some tips to publish and build a MiniStor Social Media community

- ⇒ Make sure that in all your tweets related to MiniStor you include the appropriate handle @MiniStorH2020, the hashtag #ministor and/or #MiniStorH2020, and reference MiniStor website: <http://ministor.eu/>
- ⇒ If visual design is included in your social media action, please ensure that MiniStor visual identity is followed ([Book of Style](#))
- ⇒ Other hashtags you may use: #sustainability, #innovation, #heating #cooling #electricity #H2020 #energystorage #energyefficiency #RenewableEnergy #solarenergy #innovation #tech #home #greenbuilding
- ⇒ Please share in your social media account all MiniStor tweets and posts
- ⇒ **Through your social media accounts, please follow MiniStor in Twitter and LinkedIn**
- ⇒ To create a stronger community, follow all MiniStor partners on social media. Information about each partner account below:

Name of the partner	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK - NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, CORK (Tyndall) - International Energy Research Centre (IERC)
Logo	
Website	http://www.ierc.ie/
Social Media Handles	<u>Twitter:</u> @IERC_Info <u>LinkedIn:</u> https://www.linkedin.com/company/ierc---international-energy-research-centre/ https://www.linkedin.com/in/ierc-international-energy-research-centre-b5448185/

Name of the partner	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS (CERTH)
Logo	
Website	https://www.certh.gr/root.en.aspx
Social Media Handles	Twitter: https://twitter.com/certhellas?lang=el LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/certh/

Name of the partner	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS (CNRS-PROMES)
Logo	
Website	http://www.promes.cnrs.fr/ www.cnrs.fr
Social Media Handles	Twitter: @PROMES_CNRS @CNRS

Name of the partner	FACHHOCHSCHULE ZENTRALSCHWEIZ - HOCHSCHULE LUZERN (HSLU)
Logo	
Website	Full School: www.hslu.ch Research group: www.hslu.ch/TES
Social Media Handles	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/school/hochschule-luzern/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/hslu

Name of the partner	FUNDACION CARTIF (CARTIF)
Logo	
Website	https://www.cartif.com/en/ https://www.cartif.com/ (Spanish)
Social Media Handles	Twitter: https://twitter.com/cartifct LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/cartif Youtube: https://www.youtube.com/user/CartifTV/ Blog: https://blog.cartif.com/en/ Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/CARTIF

Name of the partner	SUNAMP LIMITED (SUNLTD) and SUNAMP SWITZERLAND GMBH (SUNCH)
Logo	
Website	www.Sunamp.com
Social Media Handles	Twitter: @sunampltd Facebook: Sunamp Ltd. Linkedin: Sunamp Limited

Name of the partner	EDILIANS (EDILIANS)
Logo	
Website	https://edilians.com/
Social Media Handles	Twitter: @HelioscienceFr

Name of the partner	ENDEF ENGINEERING SL (ENDEF)
Logo	
Website	https://endef.com/
Social Media Handles	Twitter: @EndeFEng

Name of the partner	ENETECH SPOLKA Z OGRANICZONA ODPOWIEDZIALNOSCIA (Enetech)
Logo	
Website	https://endef.com/
Social Media Handles	enetech.com.pl/en Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/Enetech-1396790383765296/ LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/19038109 IG: https://www.instagram.com/enetechspzoo/?hl=pl

Name of the partner	SGS TECNOS SA (SGS TECNOS)
Logo	
Website	https://www.sgs.com/
Social Media Handles	Twitter: @sgs_Spain @sgs_SA

Name of the partner	EMI EPITESUGYI MINOSEGELLENORZO INNOVACIOS NONPROFIT KFT (EMI)
Logo	
Website	www.emi.hu
Social Media Handles	Facebook: @Emi.Nonprofit.Kft Linkedin: linkedin.com/company/emi-nonprofit-kft

Name of the partner	FAFORRAS FAIPARI KORLATOLT FELELOSSÉGU TARSASAG (WOODSPRING)
Logo	
Website	https://www.faforras.hu/kezdolap

Name of the partner	CORK CITY COUNCIL (CORKCITY)
Logo	
Website	www.corkcity.ie
Social Media Handles	Twitter: @corkcity

Name of the partner	DIMOKRITIO PANEPISTIMIO THRAKIS (DUTH)
Logo	
Website	https://medilab.pme.duth.gr/ http://duth.gr/
Social Media Handles	Twitter: @MeDiLab4 LinkedIn: @MeDiLab Facebook: @duth.gr

Name of the partner	FUNDACION EMPRESA UNIVERSIDAD GALLEGA (FEUGA)
Logo	 <small>FUNDACIÓN EMPRESA - UNIVERSIDAD GALLEGA</small>
Website	https://www.feuga.es/
Social Media Handles	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/feuga--fundacion-universidad-empresa-gallega/ Twitter: @FEUGA_20

Name of the partner	R2M SOLUTION SRL (R2M)
Logo	 <small>RESEARCH TO MARKET SOLUTION</small>
Website	https://www.r2msolution.com
Social Media Handles	LinkedIn: @r2m-solution Twitter: @R2MSolution

Name of the partner	The university of Edinburgh (UEDIN)
Logo	 THE UNIVERSITY of EDINBURGH School of Chemistry
Website	www.chem.ed.ac.uk
Social Media Handles	Twitter: @EdinburghChem

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869821

MiniStor communication strategy

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869821

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SUMMARY

The final objective of the present document is to establish a guideline about strategies, and work-flows for partners to follow when developing the activities related to communication in order to reach our target stakeholders and show them the benefits of the MiniStor project.

The European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme is aware that communication plays an important role in making sure a European project has a real and lasting impact. Besides, communication is important not only to ensure transparency and the exchange of knowledge but also to raise public awareness of the benefits of the projects financed by the European Union's H2020 programme.

This document describes in a non-exhaustive way how the project will approach communication to different target audiences, as well as the main channels and tools that will support this approach.

CORPORATE IMAGE OF THE PROJECT

EU Emblem

Projects approved under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme are publicly funded. This is a commitment to carry out communication actions to maximize their impact, and ensure the transparency and visibility of their funding, activities and results. Therefore, any communication action or material created by the project must clearly indicate the source of the funds. For this reason, all European projects must use the European emblem (flag), associated to a sentence that indicates the name of the programme our project has received funding from:

- The EU emblem - High-resolution emblems can be found here: https://europa.eu/european-union/about-eu/symbols/flag_en, and
- Must be always accompanied by the following sentence: **This project has received funding from the European Union's H2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 869821**

*The typeface to be used in conjunction with the EU emblem can be any of the following: Arial, Calibri, Garamond, Trebuchet, Tahoma, Verdana.

* It is not allowed the use of the European Commission's logo:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869821

Figure 1. Incorrect and correct usage of the EU emblem

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have an appropriate prominence.

- The EU emblem accompanied by the sentence is available on Microsoft Teams: [here](#)

Projects' logo

The project's logo must be used in all communication involving the project. MiniStor logo is available to all partners on Microsoft Teams: [here](#)

It is worth remembering that visual identity is one of the most important aspects of the project's brand. The care, normalization and homogenization of the visual identity of our project will allow us among other aspects:

- Promote stakeholder recognition
- Enhance credibility in the project's actions and results
- Ensure quality and reliability of the project
- Inspire a sense of belonging to a group with shared values

Given this scenario, we need to be aware of the need to care for the project's brand, and by extension, the visual identity of the project. These indications are a tool to achieve excellence in the use of our brand, MiniStor, avoiding deviations in the different uses.

Figure 2. MiniStor main logo (Full Logotype)

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The use of any stylized, animated, hand drawn or any other versions of an unofficial logo is not permitted. This would undermine the logo system and visual consistency.

The main logo to use is the Full Logotype (figure 2). Other versions are reserved only when the background of the page forces a different version, this is, black or negative backgrounds. Recommended formats are: .eps | .ai | .png | .jpg | .tiff

The EU Emblem will be located, preferably, on the left of the full logotype always ensuring both the MiniStor logo and EU Emblem are equal in terms of size and visibility, whenever possible.

Figure 3. Suggested use of MiniStor logo in co-existence with EU emblem

As said, if the format of the communication material background does not allow the use of the Full Logotype, partners are welcome to use a one-ink version of the logotype:

Figure 3. MiniStor logo One-ink versions

Corporate colours

Colour plays a fundamental role in the MiniStor corporate identity. The palette of primary colors below has been developed comprising a “One Voice” colour scheme. A consistent use of these colours will contribute to the cohesive and harmonious look of MiniStor identity. Check with your designer or printer when using the corporate colours to ensure they are consistent.

The corporate colours of MiniStor trademark are as follows:

MAIN COLOURS GRADIENT BLUE RED:

BLUE COLOUR CODES

CMYK: C081 M002 Y011 K000

Pantone: 638 C

RGB: R000 G173 B216

Web: #00acd7

RED COLOUR CODES

CMYK: C000 M083 Y073 K000

Pantone: Warm Red C

RGB: R233 G071 B063

Web: #e8473e

SECONDARY COLOR SYSTEM:

The Secondary colors are complementary to our official colors, but are not recognizable identifiers for MiniStor. Use them to accent and support the primary color palette.

BLACK

BLACK COLOUR CODES

CMYK: C000 M000 Y000 K100

Pantone: Neutral Black C

RGB: R000 G000 B000

Web: #000000

WHITE

WHITE COLOUR CODES

CMYK: C000 M000 Y000 K000

Pantone: White

RGB: R255 G255 B255

Web: #ffffff

GREY

GREY COLOUR CODES

CMYK: C017 M000 Y000 K050

Pantone: 443C

RGB: R135 G148 B155

Web: #87949b

Corporate typography

Typography plays an important role in communicating an overall tone and quality. A careful use of typography reinforces and ensures clarity and harmony in all MiniStor communications.

We have selected a personalized font for the logo. **The font Lato was selected for other corporate applications, if not possible, Calibri will be used.**

How to get the font Lato for your word documents? Here you can download it: <https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Lato>

Figure 4. Corporate font of the project (Lato)

A personalized font was specially created for the logo:

CORPORATE FONT 01
Personalized Font

The image shows the word "MINISTOR" in a bold, rounded, sans-serif font. The letters are thick and have a slightly irregular, hand-drawn appearance, particularly in the 'M' and 'I's.

Figure 5. Personalized font for MiniStor logotype

OBJECTIVES AND TARGET AUDIENCE

Objectives

The communication actions developed under the project will be aligned with the objectives of the project and the general objective of the H2020 programme, which is to increase Europe's competitiveness through the implementation of three priorities:

- Generate an excellent science
- Creating industrial leadership
- Addressing social challenges

The general objective should also be achieved through the specific objectives of "Spreading excellence and broadening participation", and "Science with and for society".

MiniStor addresses the topic LC-EEB-05-2019-20: "Integrated storage systems for residential buildings" through the following target outcomes and how they are addressed: "Optimised storage solutions for thermal and electric energy are needed in order to better synchronise the overall supply and demand, at residential, district and urban level. Efficient management of the peak loads would reduce the overall operational costs of the installations."

More specifically, the objectives of MiniStor can be summarized in the following points:

- Design and application of an integrated, high performing, versatile, durable and multifunctional thermal energy storage system that reduces net energy consumption for heating and cooling
- Development of a high energy density and compact TCM reactor for heating and cooling storage
- Integrate self-harvesting RES options, electrical energy flexibility and response to grid signals, offering increase of self-consumption and better synchronization of energy flows at a building level
- Improvement of building performance through a cutting-edge human-centric home energy management system
- Use of design and construction methods for decreased installation time with minimum maintenance needs

- Develop an effective storage solution with minimum environmental impact
- Deployment, demonstration, validation and evaluation of the overall solution in real-life residential sites
- Elaborate and validate circular economy-driven business models (BMs) and market design to stimulate market penetration of the developed and validated integrated storage system at European level

Taking all this into consideration, the objectives of the communication strategy of the MiniStor project are:

- To introduce and communicate MiniStor, its objectives, the consortium, countries involved, as well as the main activities and results.
- To promote MiniStor brand, in order to enable the project's identification by an established image.
- To reach as many target audiences as possible by promoting widely planned activities in order to maximize the number of stakeholders reached.

Target audiences

The main objective of the communication strategy is **to inform, reach out to society and show the benefits of the research being carried out within the framework of the project**. This approach should be communicated to the general public and to the media in particular, as the latter may actively contribute to communication activities by informing society about the impact of the project's results.

Among the general public, a key group of interest for the communication activities is the stakeholders, due to their capacity to support and promote the activities of the project, as well as their influence on the project and/or the wider target audiences.

In relation to stakeholders, the following groups are of interest:

- Public authorities, public administrations, regulators, Energy/regional development agencies
- Associations and networks of stakeholder's representatives
- Building owners, direct end users, and other type of user profiles
- RES integration developers, Consultancy companies, installers, renovators, inspectors and energy auditors, among others

- Energy services companies and thermal/electric energy companies
- Investors and financing institutions
- ICT companies and service providers (large, small, start-ups)
- Wider research community – this will be addressed through scientific publications and participation in specialized conferences. An open access model will be preferred for scientific publications

Due to the heterogeneous nature of the target audience, communication actions will be adapted, identifying the most appropriate channels, tools and messages for each of the segmented audiences to reach the total of the addressees by means of public-message-medium alignment.

COMMUNICATION MATERIALS, AND COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

The use of appropriate communication channels and tools is as important as the identification of the target audience for such communication. MiniStor will implement a multi-channel communication approach.

The criteria to be taken into consideration when classifying and selecting the most appropriate communication channels are:

- The means used for each of the target groups
- The means accessible to each target group
- The most influential, and credible media among target groups

Bearing in mind the above, and framing it within the project's needs, the communication channels selected could be classified as follows:

Table 1 Channels to be used for communication purposes

ONLINE CHANNELS	OFFLINE CHANNELS
MiniStor website	Events (own and others)
Social media platforms (academic and general ones)	Workshops (own and others)
Online Magazines and publications	Pilot sites visits
Events websites	Meetings with stakeholders, policy makers, other project representatives
Specialized and general media	
Already existing networks*	

*Already existing networks: from other project partners, associations, platforms, other projects or initiatives to which members belong and that can act as channels for sharing project activities.

Communication materials will be disseminated throughout the above mentioned channels. The following table shows the relation between materials and channels by which they will be distributed

Table 2 Relation between channels and materials

CHANNELS		COMMUNICATION MATERIALS	
ON-LINE	MiniStor Website This is the base channels for all information related to the project	Website content (General information about the project, news and events section, synergies with other projects, results, etc.) Policy briefs Project Videos	Deliverables and Infographics Newsletters Roll up and poster Brochure Press releases Media Kit
	Social media platforms (general ones e.g. twitter, linkedIn)	Dissemination of all Website content Brochure Press releases	Project Videos Infographics Newsletters
	Social media platforms (academic ones)	Articles Publications	Policy briefs
	Online Magazines and publications	Articles	Publications
	Events websites	Events	News
OFF-LINE	External Events (own and third parties)	Brochure Roll-up Poster	Materials (pen, bags, folders) PPT
	Visits to pilots	Brochure Roll-up Poster	PPT Materials (pen, bags, folders)
	Meetings with stakeholders, policy makers, other project representatives	Brochure PPT Policy briefs	Materials (pen, bags, folders)
ON-LINE & OFF-LINE	General media and specialized media	Press releases Media kit	Articles Publications
	Already existing networks	Press releases Website contents (News, events, policy briefs) Social Media activities	

KEY MESSAGES TO BE REFLECTED IN ALL COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

These key messages will be updated during the development of the project to reflect its evolution and results. All key messages will address target stakeholders through all means possible stated in table 3 (above):

Table 3 Relation between specific key messages and targeted stakeholders

Specific Key Messages	Targeted Stakeholder
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integrated, high performing, versatile, durable and multifunctional thermal energy storage system - Cost-efficient energy storage systems - Circular economy-driven business models (BMs) - Minimum environmental impact - Decreased installation time with minimum maintenance needs - Reduction of net energy consumption for heating and cooling - High energy density and compact TCM reactor for heating and cooling storage - Integration of self-harvesting RES options and electrical energy flexibility - Integration of response to grid signals - Increase of self-consumption - Better synchronization of energy flows at a building level - Improvement of building performance - Cutting-edge human-centric home energy management system 	<p>Energy services companies and thermal/electric energy companies</p> <p>ICT companies and service providers (large, small, start-ups)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support EU policies for boosting energy efficiency - Support EU policies for renovation of the EU building stock - Job creation - Circular economy-driven business models (BMs) - Minimum environmental impact - Health benefits and wellbeing - Reduction of energy poverty - Reduction of net energy consumption for heating and cooling - Integrated, high performing, versatile, durable and multifunctional thermal energy storage system - Integration of self-harvesting RES options and electrical energy flexibility - Integration of response to grid signals - Increase of self-consumption - Improvement of building performance 	<p>Public authorities, public administrations, regulators, Energy/regional development agencies</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cutting-edge human-centric home energy management system - Increase of self-consumption - Health benefits and wellbeing - Reduction of energy poverty - Increased property value - Cost-efficient energy storage systems - Reduction of net energy consumption for heating and cooling - Integrated, high performing, versatile, durable and multifunctional thermal energy storage system - Minimum environmental impact 	<p>Associations and networks of stakeholder's representatives</p> <p>Building owners, direct end users, and other type of user profiles</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integrated, high performing, versatile, durable and multifunctional thermal energy storage system - Decreased installation time with minimum maintenance needs - Cost-efficient energy storage systems - Reduction of net energy consumption for heating and cooling - High energy density and compact TCM reactor for heating and cooling storage - Integration of self-harvesting RES options and electrical energy flexibility - Integration of response to grid signals - Increase of self-consumption - Better synchronization of energy flows at a building level - Improvement of building performance 	<p>RES integration developers, Consultancy companies, installers, renovators, inspectors and energy auditors, among others</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Circular economy-driven business models (BMs) - Decreased installation time with minimum maintenance needs - Increased property value - Cost-efficient energy storage systems - Reduction of net energy consumption for heating and cooling - Integrated, high performing, versatile, durable and multifunctional thermal energy storage system - Integration of self-harvesting RES options and electrical energy flexibility - Integration of response to grid signals - Increase of self-consumption - Better synchronization of energy flows at a building level - Improvement of building performance 	<p>Investors and financing institutions</p>

Other Key messages (Impacts)

To be used in all communication materials through online channels and printed ones, events and meetings:

- ✓ Impact #1: Demonstrate solutions that have a stable, reliable long term performance in multi-cyclic seasonal and use of at least 20 years
Result: individual components have endured long-term multi-cyclic operation in their original operational environment
- ✓ Impact #2: Deliver compact systems with the potential to fit in the limited space available in a single building in the existing housing stock or new buildings. The storage material volume per dwelling should not exceed 1 m³
Result: Calculated volume of 0.72m³ of storage material
- ✓ Impact #3: Solutions should demonstrate a potential to reduce the net energy consumption of a building by at least 25% and a have return-on-investment period below 10 years
Result: Energy savings by at least 44% PE and return of investment of 6.7 years
- ✓ Impact #4: Use of high energy density storage materials allowing storage densities up to 10 times higher than water (based on overall system efficiency)
Result: Energy storage density more than 13.5 times higher than water

COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

This next chapter details the procedures that need to be developed by partners with the aim of promoting, developing and updating the communication channels and materials described above.

This document may be updated during the project' lifetime, as new deadlines or details might be added while MiniStor develops.

MiniStor- Website

MiniStor- website will be the project's main online communication channel. In order to increase the project's visibility, all partners should include a link to the MiniStor website from their own website, and share it through their social media accounts, if possible.

The main sections of the website that are subject to updates are as follows:

- ✓ ABOUT MiniStor: Information about the thematic of the project, motivation and background as well as, the objectives of the project.

- ✓ PARTNERS: Consortium information.
- ✓ WHAT WE DO: Explanation of the project's work plan in a language that is both informative and understandable to the general public. Special attention will be focused on the demo sites to be developed for validating the MiniStor system.
- ✓ KNOWLEDGE CENTRE: Specific information about the heating system, data gathering, demonstration activities, etc.
 - Materials to be included in the Knowledge centre:
 - Scientific Publications
 - Factsheets/Infographics
 - Video
 - Training sessions
 - Workshops
 - Communication materials
 - Public deliverables
- ✓ NEWS AND EVENTS: Project-related news. All relevant information regarding the progress of the project as well as related topics of interest.
- ✓ RELATED LINKS: Links to other projects, initiatives, associations or entities that have to do with the MiniStor project.
- ✓ CONTACT: Details on how to get in contact with the MiniStor project consortium. Contact form. An specific e-mail has been created for such purpose: info@ministor.eu

Two main activities should be carried out by partners in terms of maintaining the website updated and accessible to all stakeholders:

Website update (news and events):

- All partners are responsible for providing material and content to keep the website up to date. Mainly events and news as they are the most regularly updated information but also articles, publications, results and other initiatives are englobed in this section.

News items will be uploaded to the **News and Events Section** and can cover information regarding the following topics:

- ✓ MiniStor- presence at external events, such as trade events, fairs, industrial exhibitions, meetings, congresses, conferences.

- ✓ Activities developed under the framework of the project, such as pilot visits, consortium meetings and meetings with stakeholders.
 - ✓ The progress of the project, milestones accomplished newly published materials.
 - ✓ Project results and news relevant to the project's sector
 - ✓ Articles, publications and press releases, among others.
- Contents will be written in a clear and accessible language in order to reach an audience as broad as possible.
 - Partners are welcome to prepare the information to be included in the website in English and their own language, using templates available in Annex 1, and send them to iarias@feuga.es to be uploaded on the website, as well as the responsible partners for each language area (see Tab. 4).
 - News and other information can also be shared without editing, in case there is a time constrain, by simply sharing the link with the WP8 leader, iarias@feuga.es

Translation of contents:

FEUGA will take the role of webmaster. The content of the website can be translated into different languages under the request of the partners and/or the coordinator to make the information more accessible to stakeholder:

Table 4. Possible languages the website can be translated into

Translation languages	Partners in charge	Contact person
Greek		
French		
Spanish	FEUGA	Inés Arias (iarias@feuga.es)
German		
Polish		
Hungarian		
Italian		

- The website content would be prepared by FEUGA and sent to the partner in charge of the translation.

Social media management

Social media are a big opportunity to reach stakeholders as well as society in general, creating awareness for the project. About one-third of a website's traffic comes from social media.

- The general social media platforms to be used in MiniStor are Twitter and LinkedIn:
 - Twitter: it is the most popular micro-blogging site and represents the opportunity to reach people from all over the world with interests related to the project. Twitter account should be updated regularly with at least 1 tweet or retweet every day from Monday to Friday.
 - LinkedIn: it is used for connecting with people that work in similar or related fields, as well as sharing knowledge. LinkedIn should be updated regularly, with at least 1 or 2 posts every week.
- FEUGA has created project accounts and it's the responsible partner for its animation. All the information will be published in English. The information to post will be, among others:
 - News about the project, its results and outputs (e.g. materials)
 - News about the organization, participation in events, and partners' activities related to the project
 - News concerning MiniStor system and its operation
- Partners are responsible for providing contents to FEUGA. Materials that should be sent to FEUGA to be published in these platforms and could include the following, among others:
 - Photographs of activities and events carried out over the project's development.
 - Short videos or footage of the project's activities, pilots, training sessions, meetings with stakeholders
 - Interesting articles or websites that may be of interest to the MiniStor potential audience.
- All partners will have access to the MiniStor accounts upon request to share content directly. FEUGA has prepared some social guidelines available in the project's sharing platform.

- All partners should follow MiniStor social media accounts with their personal/institutional accounts. In the document Social Media Guidelines, partners can find the consortium's social media accounts in order to create an online network through different platforms.

Communication materials

FEUGA, as WP8 leader, will be responsible for the creation of promotional materials. The main communication materials to be used for creating and strengthening the MiniStor brand will be, among others:

- **Brochure**, for general communication of the project targets and showing the main objectives, expected outcomes, partners and regions involved. Brochures should be displayed at events to which stakeholders are attending to present the project and generate interest in its development and results.
- **Poster/Roll-up**: for increasing the visibility of both the project and its partners. A roll-up and a poster will be produced to be used in the activities developed by MiniStor partners and strengthen the corporate identity of the project. These roll-ups and posters can be adapted upon partners request to fit an specific purpose.
- **Power point presentation**: updated regularly. They can should be used in conferences and external events where partners are participating and should help them explain the project and how it is developing.
- **Promotional materials**: such as bags, pens, folders with MiniStor visual identity will be produced to increase the engagement of stakeholders with the project during events and meetings. Other promotional material can be produced upon partners requests.
- **Policy briefs**: a policy brief is a concise summary of a particular issue, the policy options to deal with it, and some recommendations on the best option. It is aimed at policymakers and others stakeholders that have the potential to influence on policy and regulation. These will be available on MiniStor website and ca be also distributed on events and meetings with stakeholders.
- **Infographics**: an infographic is a form of visual communication meant to capture attention and enhance comprehension. In this era, "infographic" has become the

broadest descriptor of a specific type of visual communication that includes graphics showing data, copy, or both. FEUGA will create infographics with general information about the project that can be used online or in a printed version for events and meetings with stakeholders. Partners are welcome to suggest ideas for infographics depending on their needs.

- **Videos:** FEUGA will create two general videos. One at the beginning of the project and one towards the end. Apart from these two materials, FEUGA will create short videos over the project development that will be disseminated through social media, in order to ensure the visibility of the project. For that, partners may be asked for raw footage and audio-visual resources. These videos can be used online or presented during events and meetings with stakeholders. Partners are welcome to suggest ideas for short videos depending on their needs.
- **Newsletters:** FEUGA will produce at least two newsletters per year. FEUGA will request information to partners. Partners are requested to share MiniStor newsletter through their contact. MiniStor newsletter will be available on MiniStor website and disseminated through social media.

MediaKit

FEUGA will produce a document to facilitate the presentation of the project and its progress to media. It should be used by partners to draw media attention to the project and its activities and invite them to MiniStor events. It should be updated regularly during the project. The document will be sent in English, and partners are welcome to translate it and adapt it to their regional/national language and specificities, if they wish to do so.

This document will present the project in a clear language, easy to understand for those not familiarized with the project's topic.

KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS (KPIs)

The evaluation of the communication strategy concerns both qualitative and quantitative indicators. Once measurable objectives are defined, the process evaluation will involve examining the progress of the strategy's implementation and will refer to an outreach activity that is quantifiable through the attendance of persons present from the audiences, quantity of material distributed, number of events participated, the development and dissemination of messages and materials, media presence and traffic created in social media, among others.

In order to measure the impact of the conducted activities and to be able to adjust the dissemination strategy for achieving the expected outcomes and maximising visibility, a set of initial metrics has been developed. Such metrics will allow having a regular update on the amount and the effectiveness of the activities conducted.

The tables below present the expected outcomes for each type of the activities:

Communication KPIs

Short explanatory note: The communication activities of Horizon 2020 projects go beyond dissemination: they do not involve project results only but also the project in general such as the societal challenges or European added-value of the project. Thus, communication activities target a much wider audience, including the media and the general public. It is important to use a less technical language so that a non-specialist audience can easily understand the goals and means of the project.

Channel / activity	Key performance indicators (KPI)	Common objectives
MiniStor website	Nº of visitors	1000 visitors /month in the last year of the project
	Time of visit	with +2 min staying
	Nº of news	at least 50 news accumulated.
MiniStor Social Media	Nº of followers (Twitter)	At least 700 followers
	Nº of followers (LinkedIn)	200 followers
Youtube	Nº of visits	1000 per video
Press releases	Nº of press releases	2 per project partner

Partners' existing communication channels	Nº of audience members reached	To reach an audience of more than 40,000 people (17 partners).
Leaflet	Nº of Leaflets distributed	50000
Newsletters	Nº of newsletters	2 per year
Videos	Nº of promotional videos	2

Table 5. Communication KPIs

Dissemination KPIs

Short explanatory note: Dissemination aims at maximising the impact of research results in the public domain. Therefore, the target audience of dissemination activities is any potential user of the project results: the scientific community, stakeholders, industry, policy makers, investors, etc.

Channel / activity	Key performance indicators (KPI)		Common objectives
Stakeholders & mid-term workshop, National workshops	400 stakeholders approx. attending project's events	Nº of attendees	50 per workshop
Final Conference		Nº of attendees	100 Final conference
Demonstration workshops	Nº of Demonstration workshops		3 / 50 stakeholders each
Dissemination workshops	Nº of dissemination workshops		3 / 50 stakeholders each 1 direct link to EC policy
Participation in events	Nº of international events		At least 2 per partner after 2 nd year
	Nº of national conference		2 national conferences per partner
Infographics	Per pilot site		5

Publications	Nº of publications in sector-specific magazines	1 publication/year per partner
Articles	Nº of published articles	+10 published articles (at least 1 per technical WP, open-access prioritized)
Clustering with other projects/entities	Nº of Joint actions	At least 10 joint actions within identified networks and other H2020 projects.
Policy Briefs	Nº of policy briefs	3

Table 6. Dissemination KPIs

MONITORING AND REPORTING TOOLS

A monitoring tool has been developed to effectively monitor and assess the dissemination and communication activities implemented in the project. This is based on a set of KPIs that covers all the aspects of the dissemination and communication strategy. This monitoring tool will be modified upon request of the partners to fit their needs and the projects.

The tracker at the moment includes information about publications and events but it will be updated accordingly to the KPIs approved by the consortium:

The tracker can be found in the bottom below:

[MINISTOR'S TRACKER](#)

ANNEX1: NEWS and EVENTS

[News affecting the project or any of its partners]

1. **TITLE ***

[Title for the news. News title must be descriptive and striking at the same time.]

2. **ABSTRACT, LOCATION AND DATE (max. 150 characters) ***

[Information that answers to questions WHO, WHAT WHEN and WHERE]

3. **DESCRIPTION**

[Additional information that answers the question of HOW and WHY]

4. **ATTACHED IMAGES**

[Attach two or more pictures]

5. **WEBSITE**

[If applicable, a link to a website for more information]

6. **PARTNER OR PARTNERS INVOLVED ***

[Name of partner or partners involved in the activity]

7. **COMMENTS OR OBSERVATIONS (IF NEEDED)**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 774109

MEDIA KIT

Please note this document will be updated to reflect progress through each phase of the MiniStor project.

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WHAT IS MINISTOR?

Minimal Size Thermal and Electrical Energy Storage System for In-Situ Residential Installation

MiniStor is a 54 months long project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme to offer a sustainable solution to harness the energy efficiency potential of the European building stock. MiniStor aims at designing and producing a novel compact integrated thermal storage system for achieving sustainable heating, cooling and electricity storage. Eighteen partners across the EU, Switzerland and the UK work together to harness the large potential of new and existing EU buildings providing an innovative solution for all.

Basic concepts:

The challenge and context: The residential sector accounted for 25.38% of the EU-28 total final energy consumption in 2015 and is the third largest energy consuming sector after transport and industry. Around 45% of energy in heating and cooling in the EU is used in the residential sector, 37% in industry and 18% in services. In EU households, heating and hot water alone account for 79% of total final energy use (192.5 Mtoe). Cooling is a fairly small share of total final energy use, but its demand from households in the EU is rising during summer months, a trend linked to climate change. **About 84% of heating and cooling is still generated from fossil fuels, while only 16% is generated from renewable energy sources (RES).** Bearing in mind that 75% of the energy used by this sector is sourced from fossil fuels, **decarbonisation of the heating and cooling sector is essential to reach and fulfil the EU's climate and energy goals.** The heating and cooling sector must sharply reduce its consumption of fossil fuels, while **securing energy supply and provision.** In addition, heating and cooling storage products are usually offered as separate products to the end consumer. **To contribute to address the challenges mentioned before the MiniStor system is developed.**

Why are integrated heating and cooling solutions a priority? Fulfilling the targets of Europe's energy and climate strategy: The Energy Union and the Energy and Climate Policy Framework for 2030 aim to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by at least 40% by 2030 (from 1990 levels), increase the share of renewable energy consumed to over 27% and set an energy savings target of 27% by 2030¹. However, **an estimated 97% of the European Union (EU) building stock (around 30 billion m²) is considered energy inefficient, while up to 75-85% of it will continue to be utilized by 2050.**

The majority of the existing European residential building stock was constructed before the **Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD)**, which mandates requirements for energy efficiency of buildings, including reduction of thermal energy demands in buildings. As such, there is **large potential to achieve this using solutions that can be integrated to existing dwellings** and through different measures. One of those measures, as it is the MiniStor system, is **optimizing use and management of thermal energy by allowing it to be stored to level demand peaks, increasing use of renewables affected by intermittency** such as solar-based heating. Thermal Energy Storage (TES) systems offer an increase in overall efficiency and better reliability when applied in an energy framework, leading to **better economics, reductions in investment and running costs**, as well as **reductions in carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions**. They are a flexible decentralized solution where large-scale heat transfer systems such as district heating and cooling are not practical or are too expensive to apply. However, most current systems are water-based, with the caveat that water storage capacity depends on the operating temperature difference of the heating system used, thus limiting it.

In short, what is the objective of MiniStor? In order to address the above challenges, the overall objective of the MiniStor project is **to design and develop a novel compact, integrated thermal storage system for achieving sustainable heating, cooling and electricity storage that can be adapted to new and existing residential buildings.**

Some context, why the MiniStor storage system? Current technologies for storing thermal energy include: a) Sensible Heat Storage (SHS) is the most common technology since, thermal energy is stored by heating or cooling a liquid or solid such as water, sand, molten salts, or rocks, with water being the cheapest option; b) Latent Heat Storage (LHS) using Phase Change Materials (PCMs).

In LHS, heat is mainly stored in the phase-change process (at a quite constant temperature) and is directly connected to the latent heat of the substance; c) Thermochemical Storage (TCS) is a more advanced technology, using thermochemical materials (TCM), which store and release heat by a reversible endothermic/exothermic reaction process. Reaction products can be easily separated and stored until the discharge process is required. High energy outputs are achieved, however, without adequate measures materials degrade over time reducing the output. **MiniStor uses thermochemical heat storage (TCM) technology, which is considered as a promising alternative to wide applied sensible (SHS) or latent heat storage systems (LHS), utilizing sorption and/or chemical reactions to generate heat. As a distinguishing feature, it uses proprietary technology based on ammonia reactions to stabilize the TCM materials and provide long-term operation.**

HOW DOES THE MiniStor SYSTEM WORK?

Energy Efficiency Innovation at Home

MiniStor' system optimizes the use and management of thermal energy by allowing it to be stored, levelling demand peaks and increasing the use of renewables affected by intermittency such as solar-based heating. The MiniStor system is to be demonstrated and validated in five demonstration sites located in Ireland, Greece, Spain and Hungary to test its effectiveness at different local climatic conditions.

The thermal storage system will be based on a high-performing $\text{CaCl}_2/\text{NH}_3$ thermochemical material (TCM) reaction, combined with hot and latent heat storage based on phase-change materials (PCM). The electrical storage will be a conventional system based on a Li-ion battery for flexibility and usage year-round. The storage system allows for compact storing of RES-based energy such as hybrid photovoltaic thermal panels (PVT). Furthermore, the proposed system includes a home energy management system (HEMS) to synchronise and efficiently manage the overall supply and demand at household level, responding for grid constraints and price signals. MiniStor will exploit the high energy densities of TCMs and coupled with a small PCM will provide an integrated, versatile as it will be able to store both heat and cold, as well as flexible energy storage system for buildings. It is frequent to find residential thermal storage systems having one end-use only (heating but not cooling or vice-versa), becoming idle in a household for the rest of the year and reducing its overall effectivity. MiniStor suggests a novel combination of new thermal storage materials that can be used in existing and new residential buildings, for both thermal storages i.e. cooling and heating throughout the year, increasing both efficiency and user comfort. Electrical energy storage and management increase its profitability.

MiniStor integrated storage system concep

Throughout the demonstration phase and in all locations, a series of performance key-performance indicators (KPIs) will be measured (e.g. energy efficiency, storage capacity, environmental conditions, etc.). **The system will be monitored for at least two heating and two cooling seasons** (winter and summer). **Experience gained during the first year of operation will be used to gather feedback for fine-tuning system components.** The system will be evaluated for its impact on intended end-users. **Lessons taken from the demonstration phase will be applied to create skilled workers and SMEs** that can carry out actual installation and commissioning. **Replicability of system installation across Europe will also be learned.**

The System in numbers

The system will provide stability, **performance and use of at least 20 years.**

Its estimated compact system storage material **volume is 0.72 m³.**

Overall system **storage density is extremely high, up to 10.6 times higher than water-based storage systems** for operating heating temperature difference in the range of 15oC (around 182 kWh/m³).

Flexibility will be increased with parallel use of TCM, PCM and electrical storage.

It **reduces net energy consumption of a building by at least 44%.**

The system has a **return-on-investment period of 6.7 years.**

WHAT ARE MINISTOR OBJECTIVES?

MiniStor contributes to the UN Sustainable Development Goals that are the blueprint to achieve a better and more sustainable future for all.

Multifunctional thermal energy storage

Design and application of an integrated, high performing, versatile, durable and multifunctional thermal energy storage system that reduces net energy consumption for heating and cooling.

Methods for decreased installation time

Design and construction methods to decreased installation time with minimum maintenance needs. Utilize time and cost-effective construction methods, reducing on-site installation time and disruption to occupants.

Integrate self-harvesting RES options

Integrate self-harvesting RES options, electrical energy flexibility and response to grid signals, offering increase of self-consumption and better synchronization of energy flows at a building level.

Minimum environmental impact

Develop an effective storage solution with minimum environmental impact. Economic, social and environmental issues, including comfort/indoor quality, safety and time effectiveness adopting a life-cycle approach.

Improvement of building performance

Deploy an automation framework to manage efficiently energy flows within the system and building. A home energy management system is used to improve energy efficiency in building thermal equipment.

Circular economy-driven business models

Elaborate and validate circular economy-driven business models (BMs) and market design to stimulate market penetration of the developed and validated integrated storage system at European level.

WHAT ARE MINISTOR IMPACTS?

MiniStor offers a solution that only directly benefits the energy sector but the society as a whole.

Energy savings

Energy savings of 40%
(conservative scenario)

Emission reductions

Great potential for reducing emissions by integrating RES

Job creation

New jobs associated with increased construction activity

Health benefits

Reduction of housing deprivation and air pollution

Cut energy poverty

Cut energy bills by €1,375 per year (total net energy savings of 40%)

Property value

A property with an EPC of A is worth 11% more than a comparable D-rated one

Active ageing

Appropriate heating and cooling impacts positively our elder's health and well-being

Trackable revenues

Documented cost-efficiency and reduced payback period for household owners

WHAT ABOUT THE DEMO SITES?

The MiniStor concept will be demonstrated and evaluated in an operational environment of real-life conditions in one pre-pilot and five demonstration sites, following appropriate deployment guidelines and legislations.

Deployment in these demonstration sites will be thoroughly planned, their stakeholders will be trained to maximize use of the MiniStor system. Acceptance tests of the system will be performed, allowing to validate the human-centric HEMS previous to installation.

Throughout the demonstration phase and in all locations, a series of performance key-performance indicators (KPIs) will be measured (e.g. energy efficiency, storage capacity, environmental conditions, etc.). The system will be monitored for at least two heating and two cooling seasons (winter and summer). Experience gained during the first year of operation will be used to gather feedback for fine-tuning system components.

The system will be evaluated for its impact on intended end-users. Lessons taken from the demonstration phase will be applied to create skilled workers and SMEs that can carry out actual installation and commissioning. Replicability of system installation across Europe will also be learned.

DEMO SITE 1: Cork (Ireland)

Responsible partner: Cork City Council

Climate type: Temperate with marine influence

Housing type: Social housing complex owned by Cork City Council

Construction year: 1966

Expected impact: 40% energy reduction and 1.0 m³ max. storage material

DEMO SITE 2: Santiago de Compostela (Spain)

To be updated.

DEMO SITE 3: Sopron (Hungary)

Responsible partner: Woodspring Ltd

Climate type: Continental humid climate with large seasonal temperature differences and alpine influence

Housing type: Single private house

Construction year: 2019

Expected impact: 65% energy reduction and 1.0 m³ max. storage material

DEMO SITE 4: Kimmeria (Greece)

Responsible partner: Democritus University of Thrace (DUTH)

Climate type: Mediterranean climate

Housing type: Student residences (10 units)

Construction year: 1997

Expected impact: 27% energy reduction (DHW) and 0.8 m³ max. storage material

DEMO SITE 5: Thessaloniki (Greece) – pre-demo site

Responsible partner: CERTH-ITI

Climate type: Mediterranean climate

Housing type: Demonstration platform shaped like real house

Construction year: 2017

Expected impact: It is the first smart near-Zero Energy Building (nZEB) of Greece.

THE CONSORTIUM

Eighteen partners across the European Union, Switzerland and the UK work together to harness the large potential of EU buildings to increase its energy efficiency performance by providing a new and innovative solution.

Project coordinator:

International Energy Research Centre (IERC), Tyndall National Institute (University College Cork) – Ireland

About IERC: The International Energy Research Centre (IERC) is an industry-led collaborative research centre in the field of integrated sustainable energy systems. It is hosted by Tyndall National Institute, a leading European research centre located in Cork, Ireland. The IERC delivers world leading collaborative research to meet global societal needs for secure, affordable and sustainable energy services. It enables partners to develop new products and services that will ensure real energy demand reductions across society. The centre provides an energy research environment that combines business

innovation with research excellence for energy demand side efficiency and systems integration challenges. The IERC develops its portfolio of research projects in the following priority areas: Smart Cities and Sustainable Communities, Low Carbon Heating and Cooling, Monitoring, Measurement and Analysis of Energy, as well as Embedded and Distributed Generation Systems.

The Marine Institute is a statutory government agency tasked to undertake, coordinate, promote and assist in marine research and development and to provide such services related to marine research and development, which will promote economic development, create employment and protect the marine environment. **Website:** <http://www.ierc.ie/>

Project partners:

2. Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (CERTH) - Greece

About CERTH: The Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH) is one of the largest research centres in Greece. It was founded in 2000 with its head office located in Thessaloniki. CERTH consists of five Institutes, two of which, the Information Technologies Institute (ITI) and the Chemical Process & Energy Resources Institute (CPERI) collaborate in the MiniStor project. Since its creation, it has the mission to promote the triplet

Research – Development – Innovation, by conducting high-quality research and developing innovative products and services while building strong partnerships with industry and strategic collaborations with academia and other research and technology organisations. CERTH employs more than 800 people. It has received numerous awards and distinctions such as the European Descartes Prize, the European Research Council (ERC) Advanced Grant, Microsoft International Contest Prize, the Trading Agents Competition Award and many more while is listed among the Top-25 of the EU's Research Centres with the highest participation in H2020 competitive research grants. Its research results (more than 350 publications/year) have a significant scientific impact (about 7,100 hetero citations/year) and focus on the transfer of high-quality research knowledge and advanced solution development trends, by taking into consideration the needs of industry and society. **Website:** <https://www.certh.gr/root.en.aspx>

3. Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique CNRS (CNRS-PROMES) – France

About CNRS-PROMES: The National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS) is the largest public research organisation in France, accounting for around 1 100 services and/or research units throughout the country. With more than 32 000 people (researchers, engineers, technicians and administrative staff), a 2009 budget of 3.367 billion euros, an implementation on all national territory, the CNRS is an active multidisciplinary institution that covers all fields of scientific research driving various programs and actions designed to address society and industry expectations. CNRS conducts research in all scientific, technological and societal like mathematics, physics, communications, nuclear physics, chemistry, social sciences, environmental sciences or engineering. The CNRS administration at the local level relies on its 18 Regional Delegations. Should the current proposal be retained for funding, the EU contribution will be handled by the CNRS Regional Delegation Occitanie Est (in Montpellier), which operational capacity has been largely proved (management of more than 150 EU-funded FP7 projects and 70 EU-funded H2020 projects). The research unit CNRS-PROMES (UPR8521 – PROcesses, Materials and Solar Energy) involved in this project is a key laboratory belonging to the Institute for Engineering and Systems Sciences (INSIS) and is closely associated to the University of Perpignan. CNRS-PROMES is located in three sites: Odeillo-Font Romeu (1 MW CNRS Solar furnace), Targassonne (5 MW Themis solar tower) and Perpignan. It has been involved in solar energy for more than 50 years. **Website:** <http://www.promes.cnrs.fr/>

4. Fachhochschule Zentralschweiz - Hochschule LUZERN (HSLU) - Switzerland

About HSLU: The Research Group Thermal Energy Storage www.hslu.ch/tes is a part of Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts (LUASA) – a university for applied science in central Switzerland. The research group develops and optimises thermal storage systems and their integration in residential and process heating and cooling applications. The research group performs active research on all levels of thermal storage:

- Development of novel storage materials
- Integration of storage materials into system components
- Modelling of thermal storage systems on all levels from material interaction over component integration to whole thermal storage systems
- Design, implementation and characterisation of complete storage systems
- Optimised integration of storage systems into buildings, district
- Energy data analytics
- Assessment of the optimum use of (thermal) storage in the (national) energy system

To perform this research in close collaboration with industrial partners the research group disposes of a modern laboratory for chemical analyses, a recent X-ray computed tomography system as well as a modern testing laboratory to test thermal storages under real-world application conditions.

Website: <http://www.hslu.ch/>

5. Fundación CARTIF (CARTIF) - Spain

About CARTIF: CARTIF is a horizontal, private and non-profit technology centre located in Boecillo Technology Park, in Valladolid (Spain). Its main mission is to offer innovative solutions to companies to improve their processes, systems and products, improving their competitiveness and creating new business opportunities.

CARTIF develops R&D projects, directly funded by companies or public funds raised through competitive calls for regional, national and international level. CARTIF also advises public authorities (municipalities and regional governments) in the planning and development of innovative projects with high economic returns.

CARTIF maintains the same values and objectives since its foundation in 1994 and its priority is to contribute to the development of its social and economic environment through the use and encouragement of technological innovation by the development and diffusion of research.

Its disciplinary teams work in five areas of knowledge that correspond to different economic and technological sectors: industry, energy and environment, construction and infrastructures, agrofood and health and life quality. **Website:** <https://www.cartif.es/>

6. Sunamp Limited (SUNLTD) - United Kingdom

The Sunamp logo, consisting of the word 'Sunamp' in a bold, black, sans-serif font, with a horizontal rainbow-colored bar underneath.

About Sunamp: Sunamp was founded to respond to the need for low to zero-carbon heating, cooling and hot water systems in domestic and commercial settings. Sunamp develops, manufactures, and commercializes a novel, high-efficiency heat energy storage and processing technology: the Heat Battery. This is a packaged store of heat energy which internally uses a Phase Change Material to store two to sixteen times more heat than an equal sized hot water tank. During a 'phase change', such as a transition from liquid to solid, a lot of heat or cool is stored or released. Sunamp has perfected the mechanical design that makes a Heat Battery long-lived and

easy to integrate: modular, scalable, stackable like Lego bricks and easy to connect into heating systems. Heat Batteries are integrated with various energy sources, e.g. solar PV and thermal panels, micro combined heat and power units, heat pumps, off-grid electricity, waste heat resources. This delivers extremely efficient systems for recovering waste heat and generating renewable heat. **Website:** <https://sunamp.com/>

7. Sunamp Switzerland GmbH (SUNCH) – Switzerland

The Sunamp logo, consisting of the word 'Sunamp' in a bold, black, sans-serif font, with a horizontal rainbow-colored bar underneath.

About Sunamp Switzerland: Sunamp Switzerland is a subsidiary of Sunamp Ltd. In this project, Sunamp Switzerland will be a technology provider, as its Heat Batteries will be used in the pilot plants to ensure optimal performance of the heating and cooling systems. Sunamp Switzerland will be involved in the sizing and design, integration with technologies from other partners, installation and monitoring of the thermal storages, analysis of the results. **Website:** <https://sunamp.com/>

8. EDILIANS (EDILIANS) – France

The EDILIANS logo, featuring a stylized blue swirl icon above the word 'EDILIANS' in a bold, blue, sans-serif font.

About EDILIANS: (previously Imerys-toiture) is a large industrial company (1 000 people, 300 M€ turnover) in the field of materials and components for the building industry. The main products are clay tiles for roofing applications. EDILIANS owns and operate 11 factories in France and Portugal.

EDILIANS is very active in renewable energies in buildings, in particular with BIPV tiles for more than 17 years.

EDILIANS is also developing high efficiency heat production systems to supply Domestic Hot Water and heating, operable down to -15°C. Using heat absorbers installed on roof or facade and operating all day long, the efficiency take advantage of sun irradiation. Heat pump and heat storage are part of the system. Important innovation lies in hybrid PVTh systems producing heat and PV electricity and allowing zero CO2 footprint on annual basis for the supply of DHW and heating.

Website: <https://edilians.com/>

9. EndeF Engineering SL (ENDEF) – Spain

About EndeF: EndeF is a technology-based company, specialized in the development and application of solar energy solutions for residential, commercial and industrial sectors. EndeF was set-up in 2012 in Zaragoza (Spain) and it has developed new innovative photovoltaic-thermal (PVT) panels. Currently, EndeF manufactures, markets and installs two models of PVT panels: Ecomesh and Ecovolt, that permits to optimize the energy production (thermal and electricity) to different climatic zones and locations.

With a strong commitment to «A better future», our business strategy is aligned to transform the current energy model into a model focused on people: environmentally, socially and economically sustainable. To achieve this, it distributes its efforts in four strategic lines: Engineering, Manufacturing, Installation and Monitoring that together with our R&D area, give us the possibility of working under an integral method that, through synergies between the different departments, allow us to offer solar solutions in all those phases of the process. **Website:** <https://endef.com/>

10. Enetech Spolka Z Ograniczona Odpowiedzialnoscia (Enetech) – Poland

About Enetech: Enetech is Polish company working in field of Energy efficiency and Energy storage. Founded in 2013 as a spin-off from AGH University of science and technology. We are focused on developing technology of thermal Energy storage in phase change materials (PCM). Our primary product is Mobile heat storage – solution based on PCM, that allows to transport Heat via road infrastructure instead of pipelines. Further more Enetech is also involved in work under stationary solutions of heat and cold storage in PCM.

Another area of activity of Enetech is Energy consulting. We provide highest quality Energy audits and solutions, that increases Energy efficiency of companies in Poland. **Website:** <http://www.enetech.com.pl/en>

11. SGS TECNOS SA (SGS TECNOS) – Spain

About SGS: SGS is the world's leader in certification, inspections, verification and testing. It's also a renowned multinational company with long experience in certifications for the energy sector.

The company work to achieve an improvement in the energy performance of its clients and partners.

SGS TECNOS belongs to SGS Group, a multinational company with presence in more than 100 countries and more than 94.000 employees worldwide.

As energy efficiency and certification is one of the core business of SGS work, the enterprise seeks to improve the energy performance of its clients and partners, by assuring the safety and effectiveness of energy facilities.

SGS offers a portfolio of services focused on efficiency, optimization, asset integrity and innovation. As well as, providing support across the entire energy sector with a comprehensive range of independent inspections, audits and business enhancement services. **Website:** <https://www.sgs.com/>

12. EMI Epitesugyi Minosegellenorzo Innovacios Nonprofit KFT (EMI) – Hungary

About EMI: The EMI Non-Profit Limited Liability Company for Quality Control and Innovation in Building (EPITESUGYI MINOSEGELLENORZO INNOVACIOS NONPROFIT KFT) is Hungary's largest complex institute in construction and building materials industry with more than 200 employees. Our activities are issuing technical approvals and assessments, testing, inspection, laboratory experiences (mechanical and chemical properties of materials, composites and structures, building physics characteristics, thermal characteristics as heat transfer coefficient value, impact resistance, acoustic

performance, reaction to fire and resistance to fire), research and development, certification and trainings for professionals from blue collar workers to engineers and inspectors. Working with more than 3000 clients yearly, the main mission of the institute is securing the high quality of the implementation and installations of the construction sector. In the field of innovation, we are working from applied research to the market uptake. ÉMI is an active member of many international organizations and has long experience in European research projects being active in FP5, FP6, FP7 and H2020 programmes as well.

Website: <http://www.emi.hu/>

13. Faforras Faipari Korlatolt Felelősségű Társaság (WOODSPRING) – Hungary

About WOODSPRING: WOODSPRING Ltd. is a Research SME was established in 2003 and focuses on innovative products and technologies in the energy efficiency of buildings and environmental sciences and wood and forest-based industries. The company's research and product development concern on an improvement of energy efficiency of residential buildings using smart technologies and innovative solutions to minimize building's energy consumption. There are good experience and scientific results for the quantitative measurement of natural resources used for space heating.

One of the main research pipeline of WOODSPRING is the improvement of energy efficiency of buildings. The company have participated in more building processes of test houses and development of the innovative elements such as seasonal storage system, intelligent windows system, and thermal reflecting insulation system. The controll units was developed also by the staff. The company is committed itself to preferring green and environment friendly and sustainable technologies for reducing carbon dioxide emission. **Website:** <https://www.faforras.hu/kezdolap>

14. Cork City Council (CORKCITY) – Ireland

About Cork City: Cork City is located in the south west corner of Ireland. It is the second largest city in Ireland. Cork City Council is the local authority for the city of Cork. The city recently had its boundary extended and now has a population of 210,000 people. The expanded city will allow the city to develop to meet the needs of its citizens. Cork City Council manages the cities social housing stock of over 10,000 homes. The city is a signatory to the Covenant of Mayors and has recently published its sustainable energy climate action plan (SECAP). Recently the city published its climate change adaptation

strategy 2019-2024, which includes measures to ensure that climate adaptation considerations are mainstreamed into all operations and functions of Cork City Council. Cork has cemented its place as a key European tech hub with over 300 ICT-related companies employing more than 29,000 people in the region. Cork is set to become the fastest growing region in Ireland under the countries Project 2040 plan.

Website: <http://www.corkcity.ie/>

15. Dimokritio Panepistimio Thrakis (DUTH) - Greece

About DUTH: Democritus University of Thrace (DUTH) was established in 1973, it is located in Northern East Greece and currently operates in Xanthi, Komotini, Alexandroupoli and Orestiada with 8 Schools and 18 Departments. DUTH is listed among the biggest Universities of Greece with respect to the active student population.

The Mechanical Design Laboratory (MeDiLab) was established in 2004 and it currently employs 8 research associates. Its main focus is enhancing the engineering curriculum, of the Department of Production Engineering and Management, and providing research and development solutions to the industrial sector. Over the years, MeDiLab has participated in various research programs many of them European funded.

Website DUTH: <http://duth.gr/>

Website MeDiLab: <https://medilab.pme.duth.gr/>

16. Fundación Empresa Universidad Gallega (FEUGA) – Spain

About FEUGA: The Galician Enterprise-University Foundation (FEUGA) is a non-profit, private-law entity, founded in 1982 and specialised in transferring knowledge, innovation and technology from the Galician university system to the business world and society in general.

The Foundation is a benchmark in the management of business-university relations; in the promotion and execution of collaborative R+D+i projects and in the implementation, improvement, management or certification of business innovation. **Website:** <https://www.feuga.es/>

17. R2M Solution SRL (R2M) - Italy

About R2M: R2M Solution is an integrated and multi-disciplinary innovation and consulting company that aggressively targets filling the gap between research activities and market implementation.

We excel at helping companies grow and acting as an accelerator for bringing technologies and services to the market across the fields of Innovation, Engineering, Energy, Sustainability, ICT and Innovative Products.

We invest in opportunities, conduct research, and offer pure engineering, energy services, and ICT consulting services. R2M is a strategic innovator itself and as part of its business model helps organizations and projects plan and execute the strategic use research funding carried out over a comprehensive development strategy from idea to market. In doing so, R2M provides leadership, links high performance exploitation-oriented networks, and leverages public and private funding instruments.

We actively seek spinoff creation opportunities, showcase promising technologies and build clusters for their uptake. **Website:** <https://www.r2msolution.com/>

18. The University of Edinburgh (UEDIN) - United Kingdom

THE UNIVERSITY of EDINBURGH
School of Chemistry

About UEDIN: The School of Chemistry at the University of Edinburgh and the School of Chemistry at the University of St Andrews unite together to form EaStCHEM, which delivers critical complementary research mass across aligned research themes and provides shared access to a broad suite of world-leading research facilities and expertise. Our 85 researchers deliver excellent fundamental and applied chemistry research to tackle global problems across energy, sustainability, and healthcare. Now in our 15th year of partnership, EaStCHEM's longevity attests to the shared values and collegiality of our

relationship, and initiatives in this period have brought increased links across our sites. Our students and staff are committed to harnessing their outstanding and diverse talents in the pursuit of knowledge that can be used to tackle global challenges and improve people's lives.

Website: <http://www.chem.ed.ac.uk/>

HOW IS MiniStor FINANCED?

MiniStor is a Horizon 2020 project.

Horizon 2020 is the biggest EU Research and Innovation programme ever with nearly €80 billion of funding available over 7 years (2014 to 2020) – in addition to the private investment that this money will attract. It promises more breakthroughs, discoveries and world-firsts by taking great ideas from the lab to the market. Horizon 2020 is the financial instrument implementing the Innovation Union, a Europe 2020 flagship initiative aimed at securing Europe's global competitiveness.

By coupling research and innovation, Horizon 2020 is helping to achieve this with its emphasis on excellent science, industrial leadership and tackling societal challenges. The goal is to ensure Europe produces world-class science, removes barriers to innovation and makes it easier for the public and private sectors to work together in delivering innovation.

MiniStor has been granted an overall budget of 8.628.021,25M€ of which 7.538.833,38 M€ come from the European Union H2020 programme under the agreement N° 869821 along the total duration of the project (54 Months) from 1/11/2019 to 30/04/2024.

MEDIA PRESENCE

MiniStor has a strong social media presence through its own website, Twitter and LinkedIn networks.

The news published on MiniStor's social media will follow a snow-ball effect: they will be published on its platforms (website, twitter and LinkedIn) and members of the consortium are encouraged to share the news using their own accounts to increase reachability. Several social media campaigns will take place to support key project events.

WEBSITE (www.ministor.eu)

Published Content: project results, project related news (exclusively) and events (MiniStor events and events with MiniStor presence) *MiniStor's website is currently available in English but it can be translated to other EU languages.*

TWITTER

Account: @MiniStorH2020 <https://twitter.com/MiniStorH2020>

Hashtag: #MiniStor #EnergyStorage #sustainableheating #sustainablecooling #residential #climatechange #energyefficiency #sustainability #innovation #H2020 #Horizon2020 #research

Published Content: project results (linked to the website), project related news and other news related to the topic and relevant events.

LINKEDIN

Account: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/38098733>

Hashtag: #MiniStor #EnergyStorage #sustainableheating #sustainablecooling #residential #climatechange #energyefficiency #sustainability #innovation #H2020 #Horizon2020 #research

Published Content: project results (linked to the website), project related news (exclusively) and events (MiniStor events and events with MiniStor presence)

BROCHURE

The English version of the MiniStor's brochure is available to download online: http://ministor.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/Brochure_Ministor_04.20-web.pdf Soon it will also be available in other EU languages.

ABOUT MiniStor'S IDENTITY

Four short points to maintain the project's brand: The Logo

MiniStor's logo together with the EU emblem must be used in all communication and dissemination products involving the project.

Figure 1. MiniStor main logo (Full Logotype)

If the background does not allow the use of the Full Logotype, you are welcome to use a one-ink version of the logotype:

Figure 2. MiniStor logo One-ink versions

Considering the conditions of the Grant Agreement, there is an obligation to acknowledge the EU with certain specific wording and emblems. This is a commitment to carry out in all communication actions and ensure the transparency and visibility of their funding, activities and results. Therefore, any communication action must clearly indicate the source of the funds. For this reason, all European projects must use the European emblem (flag), alongside text to indicate the name of the programme from which the project has received funding for MiniStor, this text reads as follows: **This project has received funding from the European Union's H2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 869821.** The EU Emblem will be located, preferably, on the left of the full logotype always ensuring both the MiniStor logo and EU Emblem are equal in terms of size and visibility, whenever possible.

Figure 3. Suggested use of MiniStor logo in co-existence with EU emblem

Typography and corporate colours

Together with the MiniStor logo and the EU emblem use and acknowledgment, the corporate colors and the typography play a fundamental role in the MiniStor overall visual identity. The palette of primary colors below has been developed comprising a “One Voice” color scheme. A consistent use of these colors will contribute to the cohesive and harmonious look of MiniStor identity. The corporate colors of MiniStor trademark are as follows, a gradient blue and red as primary colors:

BLUE COLOUR CODES

CMYK: C081 M002 Y011 K000

Pantone: 638 C

RGB: R000 G173 B216

Web: #00acd7

RED COLOUR CODES

CMYK: C000 M083 Y073 K000

Pantone: Warm Red C

RGB: R233 G071 B063

Web: #e8473e

The Secondary colors are complementary to the official colors, but are not recognizable identifiers for MiniStor. The MiniStor secondary colors are black, white and grey.

Regarding the typography, this plays an important role in communicating an overall tone and quality. A careful use of typography reinforces and ensures clarity and harmony in all MiniStor communications. We have selected a personalized font for the logo. The font Lato was selected for other corporate applications, if not possible, Calibri will be used.

Figure 4. Corporate font of the project (Lato)

CONTACT

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www.miniStor.eu

